

REMARK Written by O version 5.10.3

REMARK Wed Jul 3 22:58:05 1996

CRYST1 112.500 112.500 72.000 90.00 90.00 120.00

ORIGX1 1.000000 0.000000 0.000000 0.000000
ORIGX2 0.000000 1.000000 0.000000 0.000000
ORIGX3 0.000000 0.000000 1.000000 0.000000
SCALE1 0.008889 0.005132 0.000000 0.000000
SCALE2 0.000000 0.010264 0.000000 0.000000
SCALE3 0.000000 0.000000 0.013889 0.000000

ATOM	1	N	GLN	1	17.294	100.380	-15.975	1.00	97.78	7
ATOM	2	CA	GLN	1	16.278	100.628	-16.992	1.00	97.04	6
ATOM	3	C	GLN	1	15.970	99.342	-17.759	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	4	O	GLN	1	15.027	98.631	-17.401	1.00	97.70	8
ATOM	5	CB	GLN	1	16.706	101.767	-17.927	1.00	98.23	6
ATOM	6	CG	GLN	1	17.402	102.948	-17.248	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	7	CD	GLN	1	16.587	104.235	-17.209	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	8	OE1	GLN	1	15.411	104.238	-16.834	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	9	NE2	GLN	1	17.224	105.348	-17.562	1.00	93.67	7
ATOM	10	N	GLN	2	16.771	99.044	-18.783	1.00	99.66	7
ATOM	11	CA	GLN	2	16.615	97.841	-19.607	1.00	99.62	6
ATOM	12	C	GLN	2	17.751	96.806	-19.615	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	13	O	GLN	2	18.933	97.146	-19.693	1.00	99.43	8
ATOM	14	CB	GLN	2	16.116	98.169	-21.022	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	15	CG	GLN	2	14.880	99.070	-21.097	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	16	CD	GLN	2	13.539	98.388	-20.815	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	17	OE1	GLN	2	12.527	99.059	-20.593	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	18	NE2	GLN	2	13.517	97.058	-20.854	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	19	N	TYR	3	17.375	95.529	-19.576	1.00	92.47	7
ATOM	20	CA	TYR	3	18.314	94.411	-19.534	1.00	88.53	6
ATOM	21	C	TYR	3	18.350	93.586	-20.827	1.00	86.96	6
ATOM	22	O	TYR	3	18.340	94.145	-21.928	1.00	90.82	8
ATOM	23	CB	TYR	3	17.992	93.520	-18.327	1.00	86.70	6
ATOM	24	CG	TYR	3	17.741	94.295	-17.052	1.00	82.93	6
ATOM	25	CD1	TYR	3	16.557	95.000	-16.866	1.00	83.43	6
ATOM	26	CD2	TYR	3	18.699	94.355	-16.050	1.00	82.23	6
ATOM	27	CE1	TYR	3	16.340	95.754	-15.727	1.00	82.13	6
ATOM	28	CE2	TYR	3	18.488	95.098	-14.903	1.00	82.68	6
ATOM	29	CZ	TYR	3	17.309	95.798	-14.747	1.00	89.34	6
ATOM	30	OH	TYR	3	17.106	96.551	-13.613	1.00	92.52	8
ATOM	31	N	GLY	4	18.415	92.264	-20.681	1.00	67.34	7
ATOM	32	CA	GLY	4	18.405	91.326	-21.799	1.00	57.37	6
ATOM	33	C	GLY	4	17.382	90.229	-21.501	1.00	41.18	6
ATOM	34	O	GLY	4	16.342	90.481	-20.893	1.00	41.40	8
ATOM	35	N	CYS	5	17.654	88.998	-21.917	1.00	26.89	7
ATOM	36	CA	CYS	5	16.743	87.904	-21.598	1.00	25.34	6
ATOM	37	C	CYS	5	17.559	86.782	-20.975	1.00	29.61	6
ATOM	38	O	CYS	5	18.771	86.714	-21.156	1.00	35.66	8
ATOM	39	CB	CYS	5	16.061	87.337	-22.841	1.00	21.83	6
ATOM	40	SG	CYS	5	15.147	88.582	-23.788	1.00	22.28	16
ATOM	41	N	LEU	6	16.887	85.873	-20.283	1.00	24.90	7
ATOM	42	CA	LEU	6	17.612	84.756	-19.695	1.00	23.12	6
ATOM	43	C	LEU	6	18.273	83.979	-20.824	1.00	27.96	6
ATOM	44	O	LEU	6	17.947	84.150	-22.000	1.00	25.47	8
ATOM	45	CB	LEU	6	16.657	83.854	-18.910	1.00	20.32	6
ATOM	46	CG	LEU	6	16.056	84.579	-17.705	1.00	20.84	6
ATOM	47	CD1	LEU	6	17.085	84.593	-16.584	1.00	23.81	6
ATOM	48	CD2	LEU	6	14.780	83.895	-17.250	1.00	18.31	6
ATOM	49	N	GLU	7	19.236	83.149	-20.447	1.00	28.02	7
ATOM	50	CA	GLU	7	19.940	82.312	-21.403	1.00	29.16	6
ATOM	51	C	GLU	7	19.202	80.980	-21.456	1.00	32.48	6
ATOM	52	O	GLU	7	19.807	79.920	-21.305	1.00	31.92	8
ATOM	53	CB	GLU	7	21.375	82.081	-20.935	1.00	33.16	6
ATOM	54	CG	GLU	7	22.450	82.726	-21.796	1.00	43.98	6

ATOM	55	CD	GLU	7	22.407	84.231	-21.730	1.00	67.96	6
ATOM	56	OE1	GLU	7	21.297	84.759	-21.497	1.00	63.15	8
ATOM	57	OE2	GLU	7	23.470	84.865	-21.899	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	58	N	GLY	8	17.884	81.038	-21.614	1.00	28.04	7
ATOM	59	CA	GLY	8	17.104	79.810	-21.691	1.00	25.30	6
ATOM	60	C	GLY	8	16.987	79.384	-23.148	1.00	33.92	6
ATOM	61	O	GLY	8	17.049	80.196	-24.072	1.00	41.49	8
ATOM	62	N	ASP	9	16.789	78.089	-23.342	1.00	30.79	7
ATOM	63	CA	ASP	9	16.671	77.481	-24.664	1.00	33.09	6
ATOM	64	C	ASP	9	15.753	78.236	-25.611	1.00	30.11	6
ATOM	65	O	ASP	9	15.928	78.256	-26.824	1.00	36.28	8
ATOM	66	CB	ASP	9	16.067	76.083	-24.493	1.00	38.65	6
ATOM	67	CG	ASP	9	14.865	76.078	-23.559	1.00	66.32	6
ATOM	68	OD1	ASP	9	14.424	77.181	-23.167	1.00	74.72	8
ATOM	69	OD2	ASP	9	14.374	74.982	-23.206	1.00	64.77	8
ATOM	70	N	THR	10	14.690	78.763	-25.025	1.00	17.00	7
ATOM	71	CA	THR	10	13.606	79.386	-25.757	1.00	10.89	6
ATOM	72	C	THR	10	13.715	80.890	-25.962	1.00	18.40	6
ATOM	73	O	THR	10	12.953	81.487	-26.729	1.00	22.98	8
ATOM	74	CB	THR	10	12.384	79.149	-24.869	1.00	16.00	6
ATOM	75	OG1	THR	10	11.513	78.232	-25.536	1.00	23.04	8
ATOM	76	CG2	THR	10	11.693	80.453	-24.454	1.00	18.39	6
ATOM	77	N	HIS	11	14.591	81.523	-25.195	1.00	15.24	7
ATOM	78	CA	HIS	11	14.627	82.974	-25.200	1.00	16.99	6
ATOM	79	C	HIS	11	15.258	83.632	-26.406	1.00	23.33	6
ATOM	80	O	HIS	11	16.138	83.035	-27.028	1.00	32.81	8
ATOM	81	CB	HIS	11	15.320	83.471	-23.928	1.00	17.24	6
ATOM	82	CG	HIS	11	14.708	82.918	-22.682	1.00	18.82	6
ATOM	83	ND1	HIS	11	15.154	81.753	-22.098	1.00	19.49	7
ATOM	84	CD2	HIS	11	13.630	83.315	-21.967	1.00	17.65	6
ATOM	85	CE1	HIS	11	14.382	81.466	-21.066	1.00	17.68	6
ATOM	86	NE2	HIS	11	13.458	82.402	-20.955	1.00	16.61	7
ATOM	87	N	LYS	12	14.821	84.864	-26.656	1.00	13.75	7
ATOM	88	CA	LYS	12	15.375	85.754	-27.673	1.00	12.66	6
ATOM	89	C	LYS	12	16.661	86.349	-27.096	1.00	29.12	6
ATOM	90	O	LYS	12	16.973	86.169	-25.913	1.00	33.07	8
ATOM	91	CB	LYS	12	14.418	86.909	-27.978	1.00	6.98	6
ATOM	92	CG	LYS	12	12.973	86.508	-28.090	1.00	12.11	6
ATOM	93	CD	LYS	12	12.255	87.263	-29.183	1.00	16.24	6
ATOM	94	CE	LYS	12	11.862	88.655	-28.739	1.00	15.66	6
ATOM	95	NZ	LYS	12	10.592	89.017	-29.440	1.00	18.38	7
ATOM	96	N	ALA	13	17.416	87.062	-27.926	1.00	27.21	7
ATOM	97	CA	ALA	13	18.658	87.643	-27.428	1.00	27.50	6
ATOM	98	C	ALA	13	18.322	88.865	-26.590	1.00	31.07	6
ATOM	99	O	ALA	13	18.907	89.084	-25.530	1.00	30.41	8
ATOM	100	CB	ALA	13	19.547	88.056	-28.577	1.00	28.12	6
ATOM	101	N	ASN	14	17.368	89.637	-27.101	1.00	25.91	7
ATOM	102	CA	ASN	14	16.920	90.882	-26.497	1.00	24.11	6
ATOM	103	C	ASN	14	15.410	90.933	-26.606	1.00	21.47	6
ATOM	104	O	ASN	14	14.806	90.370	-27.515	1.00	23.69	8
ATOM	105	CB	ASN	14	17.394	92.063	-27.347	1.00	37.64	6
ATOM	106	CG	ASN	14	18.787	92.523	-26.988	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	107	OD1	ASN	14	19.006	93.070	-25.906	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	108	ND2	ASN	14	19.733	92.319	-27.899	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	109	N	PRO	15	14.828	91.780	-25.771	1.00	15.20	7
ATOM	110	CA	PRO	15	13.383	91.947	-25.796	1.00	13.13	6
ATOM	111	C	PRO	15	13.067	92.698	-27.079	1.00	18.87	6
ATOM	112	O	PRO	15	13.963	93.286	-27.673	1.00	24.23	8
ATOM	113	CB	PRO	15	13.118	92.834	-24.582	1.00	12.58	6
ATOM	114	CG	PRO	15	14.253	92.525	-23.656	1.00	18.64	6
ATOM	115	CD	PRO	15	15.433	92.047	-24.458	1.00	12.52	6
ATOM	116	N	SER	16	11.813	92.652	-27.517	1.00	13.84	7
ATOM	117	CA	SER	16	11.376	93.398	-28.689	1.00	13.74	6

ATOM	118	C	SER	16	9.901	93.106	-28.866	1.00	16.75	6
ATOM	119	O	SER	16	9.422	92.062	-28.429	1.00	20.76	8
ATOM	120	CB	SER	16	12.151	92.992	-29.938	1.00	19.25	6
ATOM	121	OG	SER	16	12.322	91.589	-29.959	1.00	35.17	8
ATOM	122	N	PRO	17	9.186	94.057	-29.457	1.00	14.28	7
ATOM	123	CA	PRO	17	7.748	93.927	-29.657	1.00	12.83	6
ATOM	124	C	PRO	17	7.581	92.604	-30.370	1.00	14.54	6
ATOM	125	O	PRO	17	8.451	92.161	-31.114	1.00	17.92	8
ATOM	126	CB	PRO	17	7.401	95.067	-30.614	1.00	14.97	6
ATOM	127	CG	PRO	17	8.557	96.013	-30.525	1.00	20.61	6
ATOM	128	CD	PRO	17	9.764	95.161	-30.239	1.00	15.27	6
ATOM	129	N	GLU	18	6.508	91.918	-30.029	1.00	9.35	7
ATOM	130	CA	GLU	18	6.286	90.610	-30.607	1.00	8.85	6
ATOM	131	C	GLU	18	4.780	90.637	-30.840	1.00	14.67	6
ATOM	132	O	GLU	18	4.003	90.129	-30.041	1.00	15.55	8
ATOM	133	CB	GLU	18	6.749	89.576	-29.580	1.00	9.53	6
ATOM	134	CG	GLU	18	6.727	88.147	-30.075	1.00	29.59	6
ATOM	135	CD	GLU	18	7.587	87.906	-31.305	1.00	32.27	6
ATOM	136	OE1	GLU	18	8.799	88.213	-31.276	1.00	9.92	8
ATOM	137	OE2	GLU	18	7.057	87.351	-32.292	1.00	30.43	8
ATOM	138	N	PRO	19	4.374	91.337	-31.893	1.00	18.14	7
ATOM	139	CA	PRO	19	2.965	91.539	-32.203	1.00	19.66	6
ATOM	140	C	PRO	19	2.126	90.276	-32.216	1.00	24.63	6
ATOM	141	O	PRO	19	0.961	90.315	-31.816	1.00	31.73	8
ATOM	142	CB	PRO	19	2.998	92.112	-33.624	1.00	21.61	6
ATOM	143	CG	PRO	19	4.268	91.615	-34.232	1.00	23.47	6
ATOM	144	CD	PRO	19	5.185	91.197	-33.114	1.00	21.32	6
ATOM	145	N	ASN	20	2.695	89.191	-32.735	1.00	15.42	7
ATOM	146	CA	ASN	20	1.918	87.963	-32.857	1.00	20.41	6
ATOM	147	C	ASN	20	1.477	86.991	-31.770	1.00	21.17	6
ATOM	148	O	ASN	20	0.812	85.998	-32.040	1.00	19.54	8
ATOM	149	CB	ASN	20	1.558	87.560	-34.286	1.00	39.61	6
ATOM	150	CG	ASN	20	0.676	88.582	-34.965	1.00	56.95	6
ATOM	151	OD1	ASN	20	0.925	88.976	-36.103	1.00	44.29	8
ATOM	152	ND2	ASN	20	-0.348	89.039	-34.254	1.00	46.35	7
ATOM	153	N	MET	21	1.820	87.310	-30.530	1.00	21.74	7
ATOM	154	CA	MET	21	1.546	86.473	-29.372	1.00	19.80	6
ATOM	155	C	MET	21	0.153	85.895	-29.172	1.00	20.06	6
ATOM	156	O	MET	21	-0.852	86.591	-29.264	1.00	22.51	8
ATOM	157	CB	MET	21	2.121	87.138	-28.124	1.00	20.50	6
ATOM	158	CG	MET	21	3.629	87.215	-28.251	1.00	23.80	6
ATOM	159	SD	MET	21	4.460	88.012	-26.890	1.00	31.24	16
ATOM	160	CE	MET	21	4.281	86.813	-25.567	1.00	28.64	6
ATOM	161	N	HIS	22	0.080	84.595	-28.921	1.00	18.95	7
ATOM	162	CA	HIS	22	-1.230	84.003	-28.695	1.00	20.59	6
ATOM	163	C	HIS	22	-1.494	83.944	-27.199	1.00	22.09	6
ATOM	164	O	HIS	22	-2.585	83.585	-26.768	1.00	24.24	8
ATOM	165	CB	HIS	22	-1.265	82.588	-29.272	1.00	25.12	6
ATOM	166	CG	HIS	22	-1.116	82.542	-30.760	1.00	33.57	6
ATOM	167	ND1	HIS	22	0.111	82.587	-31.388	1.00	37.59	7
ATOM	168	CD2	HIS	22	-2.039	82.412	-31.745	1.00	36.87	6
ATOM	169	CE1	HIS	22	-0.060	82.497	-32.696	1.00	36.01	6
ATOM	170	NE2	HIS	22	-1.355	82.389	-32.937	1.00	36.39	7
ATOM	171	N	GLU	23	-0.506	84.359	-26.414	1.00	17.69	7
ATOM	172	CA	GLU	23	-0.603	84.288	-24.966	1.00	16.07	6
ATOM	173	C	GLU	23	0.536	85.088	-24.345	1.00	17.48	6
ATOM	174	O	GLU	23	1.464	85.461	-25.055	1.00	18.29	8
ATOM	175	CB	GLU	23	-0.446	82.805	-24.631	1.00	17.50	6
ATOM	176	CG	GLU	23	-0.611	82.463	-23.174	1.00	37.90	6
ATOM	177	CD	GLU	23	-2.018	82.742	-22.712	1.00	39.68	6
ATOM	178	OE1	GLU	23	-2.964	82.158	-23.283	1.00	54.32	8
ATOM	179	OE2	GLU	23	-2.150	83.594	-21.814	1.00	16.25	8
ATOM	180	N	CYS	24	0.515	85.316	-23.035	1.00	14.20	7

ATOM	181	CA	CYS	24	1.566	86.093	-22.373	1.00	11.04	6
ATOM	182	C	CYS	24	1.604	87.509	-22.922	1.00	12.48	6
ATOM	183	O	CYS	24	2.653	88.146	-22.996	1.00	13.39	8
ATOM	184	CB	CYS	24	2.945	85.488	-22.617	1.00	9.55	6
ATOM	185	SG	CYS	24	3.002	83.695	-22.325	1.00	12.66	16
ATOM	186	N	THR	25	0.436	87.970	-23.345	1.00	9.68	7
ATOM	187	CA	THR	25	0.285	89.263	-23.992	1.00	10.13	6
ATOM	188	C	THR	25	0.664	90.458	-23.137	1.00	19.74	6
ATOM	189	O	THR	25	0.870	91.553	-23.642	1.00	28.00	8
ATOM	190	CB	THR	25	-1.140	89.393	-24.532	1.00	13.94	6
ATOM	191	OG1	THR	25	-2.048	88.929	-23.528	1.00	46.70	8
ATOM	192	CG2	THR	25	-1.300	88.448	-25.706	1.00	16.37	6
ATOM	193	N	LEU	26	0.789	90.234	-21.837	1.00	15.71	7
ATOM	194	CA	LEU	26	1.223	91.282	-20.925	1.00	12.80	6
ATOM	195	C	LEU	26	2.557	91.748	-21.475	1.00	18.36	6
ATOM	196	O	LEU	26	2.955	92.896	-21.278	1.00	24.73	8
ATOM	197	CB	LEU	26	1.502	90.629	-19.571	1.00	13.90	6
ATOM	198	CG	LEU	26	1.808	91.488	-18.346	1.00	18.44	6
ATOM	199	CD1	LEU	26	2.108	90.631	-17.128	1.00	19.93	6
ATOM	200	CD2	LEU	26	0.609	92.371	-18.061	1.00	14.48	6
ATOM	201	N	TYR	27	3.234	90.852	-22.186	1.00	9.38	7
ATOM	202	CA	TYR	27	4.534	91.198	-22.736	1.00	9.43	6
ATOM	203	C	TYR	27	4.668	91.560	-24.206	1.00	14.43	6
ATOM	204	O	TYR	27	5.787	91.758	-24.684	1.00	16.99	8
ATOM	205	CB	TYR	27	5.510	90.076	-22.435	1.00	13.32	6
ATOM	206	CG	TYR	27	5.408	89.694	-20.984	1.00	22.38	6
ATOM	207	CD1	TYR	27	4.821	88.498	-20.602	1.00	25.88	6
ATOM	208	CD2	TYR	27	5.842	90.565	-19.996	1.00	21.09	6
ATOM	209	CE1	TYR	27	4.749	88.143	-19.277	1.00	24.20	6
ATOM	210	CE2	TYR	27	5.757	90.219	-18.670	1.00	19.94	6
ATOM	211	CZ	TYR	27	5.191	89.020	-18.313	1.00	25.63	6
ATOM	212	OH	TYR	27	5.095	88.689	-16.984	1.00	35.63	8
ATOM	213	N	SER	28	3.554	91.630	-24.924	1.00	9.81	7
ATOM	214	CA	SER	28	3.634	91.900	-26.355	1.00	14.12	6
ATOM	215	C	SER	28	4.540	93.015	-26.864	1.00	19.38	6
ATOM	216	O	SER	28	5.352	92.800	-27.764	1.00	19.86	8
ATOM	217	CB	SER	28	2.267	91.849	-27.042	1.00	23.40	6
ATOM	218	OG	SER	28	1.401	92.833	-26.509	1.00	50.97	8
ATOM	219	N	GLU	29	4.430	94.191	-26.256	1.00	22.12	7
ATOM	220	CA	GLU	29	5.215	95.370	-26.625	1.00	17.55	6
ATOM	221	C	GLU	29	6.720	95.212	-26.429	1.00	19.80	6
ATOM	222	O	GLU	29	7.517	95.853	-27.111	1.00	28.76	8
ATOM	223	CB	GLU	29	4.692	96.577	-25.854	1.00	14.93	6
ATOM	224	CG	GLU	29	3.747	96.112	-24.753	1.00	36.29	6
ATOM	225	CD	GLU	29	2.337	96.036	-25.287	1.00	28.48	6
ATOM	226	OE1	GLU	29	1.430	95.478	-24.632	1.00	43.81	8
ATOM	227	OE2	GLU	29	2.170	96.596	-26.388	1.00	18.84	8
ATOM	228	N	SER	30	7.123	94.356	-25.501	1.00	14.34	7
ATOM	229	CA	SER	30	8.545	94.083	-25.297	1.00	19.05	6
ATOM	230	C	SER	30	8.618	92.668	-24.713	1.00	23.09	6
ATOM	231	O	SER	30	8.317	92.437	-23.543	1.00	22.17	8
ATOM	232	CB	SER	30	9.191	95.133	-24.384	1.00	23.87	6
ATOM	233	OG	SER	30	10.582	94.921	-24.195	1.00	29.30	8
ATOM	234	N	SER	31	8.932	91.698	-25.563	1.00	13.99	7
ATOM	235	CA	SER	31	8.894	90.309	-25.143	1.00	12.95	6
ATOM	236	C	SER	31	10.226	89.589	-25.281	1.00	23.87	6
ATOM	237	O	SER	31	11.033	89.921	-26.146	1.00	28.50	8
ATOM	238	CB	SER	31	7.829	89.565	-25.948	1.00	12.55	6
ATOM	239	OG	SER	31	7.966	88.165	-25.790	1.00	25.24	8
ATOM	240	N	CYS	32	10.442	88.606	-24.412	1.00	19.60	7
ATOM	241	CA	CYS	32	11.651	87.801	-24.474	1.00	17.39	6
ATOM	242	C	CYS	32	11.336	86.446	-25.097	1.00	17.56	6
ATOM	243	O	CYS	32	12.183	85.559	-25.172	1.00	15.13	8

ATOM	244	CB	CYS	32	12.290	87.638	-23.099	1.00	16.77	6
ATOM	245	SG	CYS	32	13.480	88.948	-22.685	1.00	22.05	16
ATOM	246	N	CYS	33	10.119	86.290	-25.599	1.00	16.32	7
ATOM	247	CA	CYS	33	9.802	85.034	-26.264	1.00	16.73	6
ATOM	248	C	CYS	33	9.302	85.299	-27.690	1.00	19.53	6
ATOM	249	O	CYS	33	8.677	86.334	-27.923	1.00	14.86	8
ATOM	250	CB	CYS	33	8.771	84.286	-25.412	1.00	14.14	6
ATOM	251	SG	CYS	33	7.155	85.119	-25.340	1.00	17.86	16
ATOM	252	N	TYR	34	9.574	84.403	-28.638	1.00	10.99	7
ATOM	253	CA	TYR	34	9.029	84.574	-29.989	1.00	7.27	6
ATOM	254	C	TYR	34	7.564	84.140	-29.945	1.00	12.97	6
ATOM	255	O	TYR	34	7.204	83.210	-29.230	1.00	14.81	8
ATOM	256	CB	TYR	34	9.769	83.756	-31.050	1.00	4.31	6
ATOM	257	CG	TYR	34	11.224	84.121	-31.232	1.00	10.10	6
ATOM	258	CD1	TYR	34	12.228	83.318	-30.718	1.00	11.41	6
ATOM	259	CD2	TYR	34	11.608	85.255	-31.937	1.00	10.86	6
ATOM	260	CE1	TYR	34	13.563	83.652	-30.879	1.00	14.35	6
ATOM	261	CE2	TYR	34	12.947	85.579	-32.111	1.00	8.41	6
ATOM	262	CZ	TYR	34	13.930	84.779	-31.582	1.00	17.40	6
ATOM	263	OH	TYR	34	15.269	85.083	-31.742	1.00	35.16	8
ATOM	264	N	ALA	35	6.708	84.795	-30.719	1.00	12.06	7
ATOM	265	CA	ALA	35	5.303	84.434	-30.657	1.00	12.22	6
ATOM	266	C	ALA	35	5.001	82.944	-30.777	1.00	17.86	6
ATOM	267	O	ALA	35	4.067	82.442	-30.155	1.00	25.15	8
ATOM	268	CB	ALA	35	4.468	85.272	-31.609	1.00	13.64	6
ATOM	269	N	ASN	36	5.847	82.209	-31.486	1.00	13.94	7
ATOM	270	CA	ASN	36	5.593	80.785	-31.672	1.00	14.27	6
ATOM	271	C	ASN	36	5.549	80.007	-30.360	1.00	25.90	6
ATOM	272	O	ASN	36	4.843	78.995	-30.247	1.00	27.06	8
ATOM	273	CB	ASN	36	6.617	80.170	-32.631	1.00	1.10	6
ATOM	274	CG	ASN	36	8.045	80.456	-32.214	1.00	24.47	6
ATOM	275	OD1	ASN	36	8.276	81.121	-31.199	1.00	39.10	8
ATOM	276	ND2	ASN	36	9.008	79.932	-32.972	1.00	20.59	7
ATOM	277	N	PHE	37	6.308	80.456	-29.363	1.00	15.08	7
ATOM	278	CA	PHE	37	6.273	79.725	-28.104	1.00	9.36	6
ATOM	279	C	PHE	37	4.887	79.863	-27.493	1.00	7.72	6
ATOM	280	O	PHE	37	4.252	78.874	-27.130	1.00	7.68	8
ATOM	281	CB	PHE	37	7.319	80.230	-27.119	1.00	11.25	6
ATOM	282	CG	PHE	37	7.202	79.568	-25.786	1.00	9.11	6
ATOM	283	CD1	PHE	37	7.838	78.367	-25.557	1.00	10.21	6
ATOM	284	CD2	PHE	37	6.295	80.040	-24.862	1.00	12.22	6
ATOM	285	CE1	PHE	37	7.659	77.697	-24.373	1.00	10.74	6
ATOM	286	CE2	PHE	37	6.114	79.375	-23.673	1.00	14.41	6
ATOM	287	CZ	PHE	37	6.770	78.186	-23.444	1.00	11.14	6
ATOM	288	N	THR	38	4.399	81.096	-27.439	1.00	4.28	7
ATOM	289	CA	THR	38	3.075	81.333	-26.887	1.00	3.95	6
ATOM	290	C	THR	38	2.000	80.502	-27.559	1.00	12.95	6
ATOM	291	O	THR	38	0.856	80.498	-27.105	1.00	16.63	8
ATOM	292	CB	THR	38	2.613	82.803	-26.963	1.00	10.63	6
ATOM	293	OG1	THR	38	2.200	83.126	-28.297	1.00	20.72	8
ATOM	294	CG2	THR	38	3.719	83.740	-26.515	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	295	N	GLU	39	2.307	79.848	-28.670	1.00	14.92	7
ATOM	296	CA	GLU	39	1.203	79.093	-29.255	1.00	18.20	6
ATOM	297	C	GLU	39	0.913	77.822	-28.474	1.00	20.32	6
ATOM	298	O	GLU	39	-0.217	77.333	-28.450	1.00	24.43	8
ATOM	299	CB	GLU	39	1.237	78.925	-30.778	1.00	20.29	6
ATOM	300	CG	GLU	39	2.428	78.221	-31.390	1.00	47.80	6
ATOM	301	CD	GLU	39	2.412	78.307	-32.908	1.00	82.06	6
ATOM	302	OE1	GLU	39	1.794	79.243	-33.454	1.00	38.25	8
ATOM	303	OE2	GLU	39	3.051	77.450	-33.560	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	304	N	GLN	40	1.931	77.359	-27.757	1.00	6.89	7
ATOM	305	CA	GLN	40	1.782	76.156	-26.960	1.00	3.34	6
ATOM	306	C	GLN	40	0.860	76.428	-25.787	1.00	13.91	6

ATOM	307	O	GLN	40	0.362	75.459	-25.223	1.00	22.88	8
ATOM	308	CB	GLN	40	3.125	75.730	-26.376	1.00	4.55	6
ATOM	309	CG	GLN	40	4.259	75.731	-27.372	1.00	7.11	6
ATOM	310	CD	GLN	40	5.446	74.980	-26.822	1.00	18.38	6
ATOM	311	OE1	GLN	40	5.279	74.136	-25.943	1.00	10.69	8
ATOM	312	NE2	GLN	40	6.645	75.298	-27.303	1.00	49.78	7
ATOM	313	N	LEU	41	0.687	77.688	-25.389	1.00	6.24	7
ATOM	314	CA	LEU	41	-0.163	78.048	-24.250	1.00	4.10	6
ATOM	315	C	LEU	41	-1.531	78.546	-24.678	1.00	13.50	6
ATOM	316	O	LEU	41	-2.424	78.803	-23.865	1.00	14.17	8
ATOM	317	CB	LEU	41	0.462	79.200	-23.462	1.00	2.20	6
ATOM	318	CG	LEU	41	1.929	78.852	-23.226	1.00	5.58	6
ATOM	319	CD1	LEU	41	2.558	79.782	-22.214	1.00	8.69	6
ATOM	320	CD2	LEU	41	1.785	77.495	-22.593	1.00	12.31	6
ATOM	321	N	ALA	42	-1.649	78.760	-25.980	1.00	13.69	7
ATOM	322	CA	ALA	42	-2.862	79.355	-26.508	1.00	10.70	6
ATOM	323	C	ALA	42	-4.163	78.628	-26.224	1.00	19.52	6
ATOM	324	O	ALA	42	-5.213	79.267	-26.167	1.00	28.04	8
ATOM	325	CB	ALA	42	-2.714	79.643	-27.980	1.00	10.16	6
ATOM	326	N	HIS	43	-4.115	77.310	-26.064	1.00	15.76	7
ATOM	327	CA	HIS	43	-5.352	76.570	-25.838	1.00	13.29	6
ATOM	328	C	HIS	43	-5.351	75.647	-24.630	1.00	21.56	6
ATOM	329	O	HIS	43	-4.375	74.946	-24.351	1.00	28.33	8
ATOM	330	CB	HIS	43	-5.736	75.751	-27.080	1.00	14.56	6
ATOM	331	CG	HIS	43	-6.077	76.587	-28.272	1.00	19.34	6
ATOM	332	ND1	HIS	43	-5.195	76.801	-29.309	1.00	20.77	7
ATOM	333	CD2	HIS	43	-7.210	77.254	-28.594	1.00	20.72	6
ATOM	334	CE1	HIS	43	-5.755	77.604	-30.197	1.00	19.23	6
ATOM	335	NE2	HIS	43	-6.976	77.890	-29.787	1.00	19.54	7
ATOM	336	N	SER	44	-6.504	75.594	-23.974	1.00	18.96	7
ATOM	337	CA	SER	44	-6.672	74.747	-22.802	1.00	20.06	6
ATOM	338	C	SER	44	-7.386	73.470	-23.233	1.00	23.29	6
ATOM	339	O	SER	44	-8.183	73.515	-24.161	1.00	31.52	8
ATOM	340	CB	SER	44	-7.504	75.502	-21.768	1.00	20.37	6
ATOM	341	OG	SER	44	-7.169	75.094	-20.456	1.00	51.38	8
ATOM	342	N	PRO	45	-7.131	72.334	-22.596	1.00	14.94	7
ATOM	343	CA	PRO	45	-6.201	72.209	-21.483	1.00	11.72	6
ATOM	344	C	PRO	45	-4.768	72.193	-21.982	1.00	11.15	6
ATOM	345	O	PRO	45	-4.501	71.669	-23.059	1.00	17.13	8
ATOM	346	CB	PRO	45	-6.516	70.804	-20.967	1.00	12.40	6
ATOM	347	CG	PRO	45	-6.925	70.070	-22.192	1.00	15.16	6
ATOM	348	CD	PRO	45	-7.830	71.063	-22.856	1.00	11.32	6
ATOM	349	N	ILE	46	-3.862	72.723	-21.169	1.00	8.34	7
ATOM	350	CA	ILE	46	-2.436	72.731	-21.479	1.00	9.10	6
ATOM	351	C	ILE	46	-1.842	71.426	-20.951	1.00	15.05	6
ATOM	352	O	ILE	46	-1.734	71.221	-19.747	1.00	20.38	8
ATOM	353	CB	ILE	46	-1.776	73.949	-20.813	1.00	11.76	6
ATOM	354	CG1	ILE	46	-2.324	75.226	-21.451	1.00	9.07	6
ATOM	355	CG2	ILE	46	-0.261	73.867	-20.879	1.00	14.21	6
ATOM	356	CD1	ILE	46	-1.867	76.489	-20.784	1.00	18.40	6
ATOM	357	N	ILE	47	-1.533	70.494	-21.843	1.00	8.43	7
ATOM	358	CA	ILE	47	-1.017	69.199	-21.425	1.00	6.34	6
ATOM	359	C	ILE	47	0.499	69.190	-21.254	1.00	9.89	6
ATOM	360	O	ILE	47	1.038	68.618	-20.305	1.00	8.85	8
ATOM	361	CB	ILE	47	-1.403	68.111	-22.459	1.00	9.15	6
ATOM	362	CG1	ILE	47	-2.915	68.093	-22.671	1.00	9.29	6
ATOM	363	CG2	ILE	47	-0.952	66.719	-22.014	1.00	4.72	6
ATOM	364	CD1	ILE	47	-3.683	67.594	-21.458	1.00	7.27	6
ATOM	365	N	LYS	48	1.191	69.795	-22.211	1.00	5.59	7
ATOM	366	CA	LYS	48	2.645	69.770	-22.213	1.00	2.66	6
ATOM	367	C	LYS	48	3.168	71.084	-22.772	1.00	13.10	6
ATOM	368	O	LYS	48	2.743	71.524	-23.841	1.00	20.07	8
ATOM	369	CB	LYS	48	3.086	68.643	-23.147	1.00	1.00	6

ATOM	370	CG	LYS	48	4.583	68.532	-23.349	1.00	7.01	6
ATOM	371	CD	LYS	48	4.888	67.290	-24.158	1.00	6.75	6
ATOM	372	CE	LYS	48	6.386	67.112	-24.312	1.00	12.21	6
ATOM	373	NZ	LYS	48	6.697	66.413	-25.591	1.00	35.93	7
ATOM	374	N	VAL	49	4.066	71.719	-22.032	1.00	11.85	7
ATOM	375	CA	VAL	49	4.690	72.957	-22.471	1.00	8.38	6
ATOM	376	C	VAL	49	6.144	72.566	-22.606	1.00	14.51	6
ATOM	377	O	VAL	49	6.749	72.173	-21.615	1.00	11.66	8
ATOM	378	CB	VAL	49	4.636	74.030	-21.381	1.00	7.27	6
ATOM	379	CG1	VAL	49	5.405	75.254	-21.835	1.00	6.09	6
ATOM	380	CG2	VAL	49	3.187	74.366	-21.110	1.00	9.26	6
ATOM	381	N	SER	50	6.624	72.541	-23.843	1.00	18.70	7
ATOM	382	CA	SER	50	8.005	72.214	-24.153	1.00	19.63	6
ATOM	383	C	SER	50	8.555	71.097	-23.296	1.00	25.35	6
ATOM	384	O	SER	50	9.133	71.365	-22.242	1.00	34.36	8
ATOM	385	CB	SER	50	8.855	73.442	-23.810	1.00	31.47	6
ATOM	386	OG	SER	50	10.187	73.110	-23.453	1.00	36.77	8
ATOM	387	N	ASN	51	8.395	69.841	-23.673	1.00	23.09	7
ATOM	388	CA	ASN	51	9.042	68.881	-22.781	1.00	29.78	6
ATOM	389	C	ASN	51	8.614	68.725	-21.324	1.00	27.47	6
ATOM	390	O	ASN	51	9.215	67.931	-20.602	1.00	34.75	8
ATOM	391	CB	ASN	51	10.560	69.079	-22.771	1.00	35.37	6
ATOM	392	CG	ASN	51	11.270	68.135	-23.718	1.00	82.88	6
ATOM	393	OD1	ASN	51	10.648	67.297	-24.378	1.00	90.23	8
ATOM	394	ND2	ASN	51	12.590	68.260	-23.778	1.00	78.77	7
ATOM	395	N	SER	52	7.583	69.435	-20.878	1.00	16.20	7
ATOM	396	CA	SER	52	7.130	69.242	-19.512	1.00	8.07	6
ATOM	397	C	SER	52	5.629	69.054	-19.473	1.00	8.70	6
ATOM	398	O	SER	52	4.881	69.980	-19.792	1.00	11.11	8
ATOM	399	CB	SER	52	7.480	70.432	-18.629	1.00	5.70	6
ATOM	400	OG	SER	52	8.847	70.346	-18.260	1.00	4.94	8
ATOM	401	N	TYR	53	5.215	67.859	-19.060	1.00	1.00	7
ATOM	402	CA	TYR	53	3.795	67.576	-18.921	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	403	C	TYR	53	3.261	68.305	-17.700	1.00	10.75	6
ATOM	404	O	TYR	53	3.921	68.336	-16.666	1.00	14.08	8
ATOM	405	CB	TYR	53	3.563	66.084	-18.748	1.00	1.43	6
ATOM	406	CG	TYR	53	3.496	65.378	-20.069	1.00	5.68	6
ATOM	407	CD1	TYR	53	4.639	64.835	-20.636	1.00	8.70	6
ATOM	408	CD2	TYR	53	2.313	65.336	-20.791	1.00	11.09	6
ATOM	409	CE1	TYR	53	4.592	64.213	-21.870	1.00	8.57	6
ATOM	410	CE2	TYR	53	2.263	64.741	-22.044	1.00	11.83	6
ATOM	411	CZ	TYR	53	3.401	64.156	-22.562	1.00	12.02	6
ATOM	412	OH	TYR	53	3.362	63.507	-23.774	1.00	16.98	8
ATOM	413	N	TRP	54	2.105	68.946	-17.822	1.00	5.76	7
ATOM	414	CA	TRP	54	1.520	69.631	-16.678	1.00	3.64	6
ATOM	415	C	TRP	54	0.368	68.793	-16.140	1.00	8.72	6
ATOM	416	O	TRP	54	-0.503	69.300	-15.439	1.00	9.43	8
ATOM	417	CB	TRP	54	0.923	70.954	-17.140	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	418	CG	TRP	54	1.946	71.973	-17.362	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	419	CD1	TRP	54	3.278	71.775	-17.475	1.00	2.91	6
ATOM	420	CD2	TRP	54	1.724	73.374	-17.460	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	421	NE1	TRP	54	3.911	72.981	-17.644	1.00	1.00	7
ATOM	422	CE2	TRP	54	2.973	73.979	-17.636	1.00	1.23	6
ATOM	423	CE3	TRP	54	0.584	74.173	-17.444	1.00	2.69	6
ATOM	424	CZ2	TRP	54	3.120	75.352	-17.787	1.00	1.14	6
ATOM	425	CZ3	TRP	54	0.732	75.530	-17.583	1.00	3.28	6
ATOM	426	CH2	TRP	54	1.987	76.109	-17.748	1.00	2.58	6
ATOM	427	N	ASN	55	0.273	67.542	-16.569	1.00	3.65	7
ATOM	428	CA	ASN	55	-0.878	66.761	-16.145	1.00	2.78	6
ATOM	429	C	ASN	55	-0.525	65.478	-15.410	1.00	8.94	6
ATOM	430	O	ASN	55	-1.374	64.606	-15.239	1.00	13.21	8
ATOM	431	CB	ASN	55	-1.766	66.471	-17.354	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	432	CG	ASN	55	-1.128	65.511	-18.332	1.00	6.21	6

ATOM	433	OD1	ASN	55	0.089	65.309	-18.351	1.00	10.83	8
ATOM	434	ND2	ASN	55	-1.976	64.852	-19.108	1.00	12.59	7
ATOM	435	N	ARG	56	0.722	65.387	-14.958	1.00	9.72	7
ATOM	436	CA	ARG	56	1.203	64.193	-14.277	1.00	7.50	6
ATOM	437	C	ARG	56	0.265	63.616	-13.223	1.00	17.82	6
ATOM	438	O	ARG	56	0.075	62.401	-13.155	1.00	26.40	8
ATOM	439	CB	ARG	56	2.611	64.409	-13.744	1.00	3.20	6
ATOM	440	CG	ARG	56	3.613	64.525	-14.864	1.00	9.48	6
ATOM	441	CD	ARG	56	3.187	63.573	-15.960	1.00	14.17	6
ATOM	442	NE	ARG	56	4.327	63.206	-16.793	1.00	16.10	7
ATOM	443	CZ	ARG	56	4.220	62.633	-17.987	1.00	28.86	6
ATOM	444	NH1	ARG	56	3.016	62.357	-18.487	1.00	14.87	7
ATOM	445	NH2	ARG	56	5.334	62.362	-18.655	1.00	4.54	7
ATOM	446	N	CYS	57	-0.359	64.476	-12.424	1.00	10.26	7
ATOM	447	CA	CYS	57	-1.284	63.940	-11.434	1.00	10.91	6
ATOM	448	C	CYS	57	-2.711	64.316	-11.799	1.00	17.35	6
ATOM	449	O	CYS	57	-3.563	64.458	-10.925	1.00	19.48	8
ATOM	450	CB	CYS	57	-0.943	64.431	-10.027	1.00	7.59	6
ATOM	451	SG	CYS	57	0.745	63.992	-9.502	1.00	12.75	16
ATOM	452	N	GLY	58	-2.972	64.504	-13.088	1.00	10.56	7
ATOM	453	CA	GLY	58	-4.297	64.919	-13.550	1.00	6.89	6
ATOM	454	C	GLY	58	-4.246	66.275	-14.226	1.00	12.64	6
ATOM	455	O	GLY	58	-3.277	66.999	-14.033	1.00	21.13	8
ATOM	456	N	GLN	59	-5.244	66.591	-15.042	1.00	13.72	7
ATOM	457	CA	GLN	59	-5.247	67.834	-15.801	1.00	12.49	6
ATOM	458	C	GLN	59	-5.542	68.863	-14.736	1.00	15.55	6
ATOM	459	O	GLN	59	-6.413	68.627	-13.902	1.00	19.68	8
ATOM	460	CB	GLN	59	-6.420	67.900	-16.788	1.00	12.41	6
ATOM	461	CG	GLN	59	-6.156	67.390	-18.205	1.00	41.49	6
ATOM	462	CD	GLN	59	-7.335	67.608	-19.142	1.00	54.51	6
ATOM	463	OE1	GLN	59	-8.202	68.450	-18.878	1.00	30.39	8
ATOM	464	NE2	GLN	59	-7.377	66.844	-20.236	1.00	28.44	7
ATOM	465	N	LEU	60	-4.876	70.006	-14.802	1.00	5.82	7
ATOM	466	CA	LEU	60	-5.203	71.022	-13.818	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	467	C	LEU	60	-6.571	71.649	-14.054	1.00	10.78	6
ATOM	468	O	LEU	60	-7.037	71.766	-15.185	1.00	14.04	8
ATOM	469	CB	LEU	60	-4.174	72.139	-13.949	1.00	1.51	6
ATOM	470	CG	LEU	60	-2.813	71.595	-13.534	1.00	7.17	6
ATOM	471	CD1	LEU	60	-1.880	72.779	-13.396	1.00	2.78	6
ATOM	472	CD2	LEU	60	-3.077	70.918	-12.195	1.00	10.59	6
ATOM	473	N	SER	61	-7.143	72.174	-12.977	1.00	12.13	7
ATOM	474	CA	SER	61	-8.370	72.965	-12.992	1.00	10.98	6
ATOM	475	C	SER	61	-8.019	74.246	-13.752	1.00	17.20	6
ATOM	476	O	SER	61	-6.849	74.642	-13.817	1.00	18.50	8
ATOM	477	CB	SER	61	-8.780	73.292	-11.553	1.00	10.27	6
ATOM	478	OG	SER	61	-7.899	74.219	-10.941	1.00	17.78	8
ATOM	479	N	LYS	62	-9.024	74.892	-14.338	1.00	9.20	7
ATOM	480	CA	LYS	62	-8.737	76.036	-15.185	1.00	9.16	6
ATOM	481	C	LYS	62	-7.930	77.097	-14.475	1.00	6.95	6
ATOM	482	O	LYS	62	-6.899	77.564	-14.963	1.00	9.12	8
ATOM	483	CB	LYS	62	-10.012	76.681	-15.720	1.00	18.72	6
ATOM	484	CG	LYS	62	-9.741	77.642	-16.868	1.00	54.11	6
ATOM	485	CD	LYS	62	-8.549	77.151	-17.680	1.00	73.07	6
ATOM	486	CE	LYS	62	-7.965	78.255	-18.544	1.00	84.09	6
ATOM	487	NZ	LYS	62	-6.479	78.181	-18.618	1.00	70.41	7
ATOM	488	N	SER	63	-8.450	77.439	-13.306	1.00	2.01	7
ATOM	489	CA	SER	63	-7.904	78.488	-12.457	1.00	3.84	6
ATOM	490	C	SER	63	-6.461	78.205	-12.087	1.00	8.58	6
ATOM	491	O	SER	63	-5.588	79.073	-12.134	1.00	13.75	8
ATOM	492	CB	SER	63	-8.741	78.500	-11.182	1.00	9.54	6
ATOM	493	OG	SER	63	-9.782	77.541	-11.321	1.00	43.34	8
ATOM	494	N	CYS	64	-6.227	76.965	-11.684	1.00	4.32	7
ATOM	495	CA	CYS	64	-4.883	76.598	-11.272	1.00	5.21	6

ATOM	496	C	CYS	64	-4.027	76.704	-12.527	1.00	6.15	6
ATOM	497	O	CYS	64	-2.920	77.253	-12.497	1.00	4.42	8
ATOM	498	CB	CYS	64	-4.893	75.170	-10.730	1.00	7.73	6
ATOM	499	SG	CYS	64	-3.270	74.592	-10.147	1.00	12.86	16
ATOM	500	N	GLU	65	-4.591	76.237	-13.638	1.00	3.78	7
ATOM	501	CA	GLU	65	-3.888	76.285	-14.915	1.00	4.15	6
ATOM	502	C	GLU	65	-3.513	77.717	-15.254	1.00	10.58	6
ATOM	503	O	GLU	65	-2.421	78.017	-15.743	1.00	12.63	8
ATOM	504	CB	GLU	65	-4.779	75.772	-16.039	1.00	4.44	6
ATOM	505	CG	GLU	65	-4.010	75.742	-17.343	1.00	13.78	6
ATOM	506	CD	GLU	65	-4.838	75.181	-18.479	1.00	25.17	6
ATOM	507	OE1	GLU	65	-4.876	73.950	-18.698	1.00	11.55	8
ATOM	508	OE2	GLU	65	-5.499	76.015	-19.128	1.00	11.31	8
ATOM	509	N	ASP	66	-4.444	78.611	-14.950	1.00	3.10	7
ATOM	510	CA	ASP	66	-4.194	80.006	-15.250	1.00	6.66	6
ATOM	511	C	ASP	66	-3.054	80.615	-14.459	1.00	11.00	6
ATOM	512	O	ASP	66	-2.256	81.360	-15.012	1.00	13.81	8
ATOM	513	CB	ASP	66	-5.477	80.822	-15.133	1.00	14.56	6
ATOM	514	CG	ASP	66	-6.559	80.302	-16.057	1.00	54.77	6
ATOM	515	OD1	ASP	66	-6.243	80.018	-17.232	1.00	55.39	8
ATOM	516	OD2	ASP	66	-7.706	80.137	-15.592	1.00	83.07	8
ATOM	517	N	PHE	67	-2.950	80.322	-13.169	1.00	8.42	7
ATOM	518	CA	PHE	67	-1.838	80.910	-12.433	1.00	6.70	6
ATOM	519	C	PHE	67	-0.513	80.340	-12.896	1.00	8.98	6
ATOM	520	O	PHE	67	0.518	81.003	-12.922	1.00	11.10	8
ATOM	521	CB	PHE	67	-2.020	80.693	-10.942	1.00	7.91	6
ATOM	522	CG	PHE	67	-2.983	81.670	-10.357	1.00	9.13	6
ATOM	523	CD1	PHE	67	-4.342	81.431	-10.443	1.00	16.75	6
ATOM	524	CD2	PHE	67	-2.536	82.896	-9.903	1.00	8.71	6
ATOM	525	CE1	PHE	67	-5.247	82.352	-9.951	1.00	17.77	6
ATOM	526	CE2	PHE	67	-3.431	83.817	-9.411	1.00	10.23	6
ATOM	527	CZ	PHE	67	-4.785	83.557	-9.461	1.00	10.09	6
ATOM	528	N	THR	68	-0.581	79.083	-13.300	1.00	9.56	7
ATOM	529	CA	THR	68	0.596	78.383	-13.779	1.00	11.43	6
ATOM	530	C	THR	68	1.074	79.027	-15.081	1.00	14.25	6
ATOM	531	O	THR	68	2.250	79.373	-15.243	1.00	8.99	8
ATOM	532	CB	THR	68	0.187	76.908	-13.905	1.00	13.32	6
ATOM	533	OG1	THR	68	-0.481	76.522	-12.694	1.00	5.27	8
ATOM	534	CG2	THR	68	1.394	76.011	-14.124	1.00	5.85	6
ATOM	535	N	LYS	69	0.121	79.235	-15.982	1.00	9.45	7
ATOM	536	CA	LYS	69	0.365	79.907	-17.253	1.00	5.15	6
ATOM	537	C	LYS	69	1.066	81.239	-16.964	1.00	6.18	6
ATOM	538	O	LYS	69	2.139	81.511	-17.496	1.00	6.04	8
ATOM	539	CB	LYS	69	-0.995	80.127	-17.911	1.00	6.85	6
ATOM	540	CG	LYS	69	-1.058	80.036	-19.416	1.00	4.77	6
ATOM	541	CD	LYS	69	-2.242	80.865	-19.902	1.00	8.89	6
ATOM	542	CE	LYS	69	-3.605	80.208	-19.722	1.00	34.57	6
ATOM	543	NZ	LYS	69	-4.121	79.558	-20.966	1.00	62.58	7
ATOM	544	N	LYS	70	0.534	82.040	-16.045	1.00	3.43	7
ATOM	545	CA	LYS	70	1.182	83.296	-15.665	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	546	C	LYS	70	2.637	83.106	-15.249	1.00	6.99	6
ATOM	547	O	LYS	70	3.495	83.925	-15.562	1.00	12.82	8
ATOM	548	CB	LYS	70	0.450	83.972	-14.506	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	549	CG	LYS	70	-0.915	84.516	-14.850	1.00	8.76	6
ATOM	550	CD	LYS	70	-1.602	85.005	-13.590	1.00	22.23	6
ATOM	551	CE	LYS	70	-3.055	85.362	-13.862	1.00	34.42	6
ATOM	552	NZ	LYS	70	-3.171	86.759	-14.364	1.00	56.62	7
ATOM	553	N	ILE	71	2.940	82.059	-14.496	1.00	1.00	7
ATOM	554	CA	ILE	71	4.333	81.874	-14.141	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	555	C	ILE	71	5.165	81.502	-15.367	1.00	8.78	6
ATOM	556	O	ILE	71	6.301	81.968	-15.473	1.00	5.24	8
ATOM	557	CB	ILE	71	4.479	80.846	-13.002	1.00	8.81	6
ATOM	558	CG1	ILE	71	3.775	81.380	-11.753	1.00	13.19	6

ATOM	559	CG2	ILE	71	5.951	80.555	-12.710	1.00	4.95	6
ATOM	560	CD1	ILE	71	4.541	82.507	-11.082	1.00	6.00	6
ATOM	561	N	GLU	72	4.639	80.690	-16.290	1.00	5.46	7
ATOM	562	CA	GLU	72	5.432	80.298	-17.462	1.00	5.41	6
ATOM	563	C	GLU	72	5.727	81.513	-18.332	1.00	10.83	6
ATOM	564	O	GLU	72	6.847	81.706	-18.818	1.00	11.85	8
ATOM	565	CB	GLU	72	4.801	79.218	-18.355	1.00	4.91	6
ATOM	566	CG	GLU	72	5.066	77.786	-17.920	1.00	21.38	6
ATOM	567	CD	GLU	72	6.301	77.187	-18.551	1.00	21.22	6
ATOM	568	OE1	GLU	72	6.784	77.851	-19.486	1.00	11.52	8
ATOM	569	OE2	GLU	72	6.752	76.089	-18.138	1.00	45.09	8
ATOM	570	N	CYS	73	4.680	82.304	-18.529	1.00	1.87	7
ATOM	571	CA	CYS	73	4.784	83.483	-19.371	1.00	5.75	6
ATOM	572	C	CYS	73	5.872	84.365	-18.780	1.00	13.56	6
ATOM	573	O	CYS	73	6.687	84.933	-19.501	1.00	12.03	8
ATOM	574	CB	CYS	73	3.444	84.213	-19.418	1.00	5.95	6
ATOM	575	SG	CYS	73	2.181	83.451	-20.487	1.00	11.84	16
ATOM	576	N	PHE	74	5.909	84.431	-17.455	1.00	15.01	7
ATOM	577	CA	PHE	74	6.877	85.285	-16.780	1.00	10.22	6
ATOM	578	C	PHE	74	8.262	84.755	-17.095	1.00	7.77	6
ATOM	579	O	PHE	74	9.132	85.477	-17.568	1.00	9.49	8
ATOM	580	CB	PHE	74	6.656	85.319	-15.259	1.00	7.44	6
ATOM	581	CG	PHE	74	7.743	86.045	-14.526	1.00	5.78	6
ATOM	582	CD1	PHE	74	7.786	87.428	-14.539	1.00	5.10	6
ATOM	583	CD2	PHE	74	8.823	85.354	-14.000	1.00	6.60	6
ATOM	584	CE1	PHE	74	8.852	88.109	-13.978	1.00	1.36	6
ATOM	585	CE2	PHE	74	9.895	86.035	-13.434	1.00	7.33	6
ATOM	586	CZ	PHE	74	9.908	87.412	-13.424	1.00	3.03	6
ATOM	587	N	TYR	75	8.479	83.488	-16.775	1.00	8.09	7
ATOM	588	CA	TYR	75	9.802	82.928	-16.978	1.00	6.62	6
ATOM	589	C	TYR	75	10.209	82.987	-18.441	1.00	15.01	6
ATOM	590	O	TYR	75	11.355	83.265	-18.781	1.00	16.02	8
ATOM	591	CB	TYR	75	9.821	81.481	-16.514	1.00	5.05	6
ATOM	592	CG	TYR	75	11.125	80.821	-16.881	1.00	5.99	6
ATOM	593	CD1	TYR	75	11.212	80.006	-17.997	1.00	7.85	6
ATOM	594	CD2	TYR	75	12.273	81.045	-16.138	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	595	CE1	TYR	75	12.391	79.381	-18.316	1.00	5.83	6
ATOM	596	CE2	TYR	75	13.471	80.480	-16.501	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	597	CZ	TYR	75	13.517	79.619	-17.566	1.00	9.47	6
ATOM	598	OH	TYR	75	14.692	78.999	-17.931	1.00	14.04	8
ATOM	599	N	ARG	76	9.235	82.760	-19.312	1.00	17.44	7
ATOM	600	CA	ARG	76	9.504	82.728	-20.745	1.00	18.49	6
ATOM	601	C	ARG	76	9.494	84.019	-21.561	1.00	21.49	6
ATOM	602	O	ARG	76	10.268	84.146	-22.510	1.00	19.24	8
ATOM	603	CB	ARG	76	8.624	81.663	-21.400	1.00	10.12	6
ATOM	604	CG	ARG	76	8.674	80.383	-20.613	1.00	21.60	6
ATOM	605	CD	ARG	76	8.779	79.216	-21.551	1.00	9.44	6
ATOM	606	NE	ARG	76	10.137	78.772	-21.842	1.00	16.96	7
ATOM	607	CZ	ARG	76	10.609	77.569	-21.532	1.00	15.50	6
ATOM	608	NH1	ARG	76	9.891	76.720	-20.804	1.00	18.06	7
ATOM	609	NH2	ARG	76	11.819	77.222	-21.946	1.00	16.48	7
ATOM	610	N	CYS	77	8.561	84.915	-21.255	1.00	14.61	7
ATOM	611	CA	CYS	77	8.380	86.153	-21.994	1.00	11.78	6
ATOM	612	C	CYS	77	8.697	87.467	-21.303	1.00	23.31	6
ATOM	613	O	CYS	77	8.769	88.472	-22.003	1.00	29.66	8
ATOM	614	CB	CYS	77	6.960	86.229	-22.543	1.00	13.13	6
ATOM	615	SG	CYS	77	6.523	84.718	-23.454	1.00	19.33	16
ATOM	616	N	SER	78	8.836	87.502	-19.980	1.00	20.15	7
ATOM	617	CA	SER	78	9.170	88.756	-19.305	1.00	18.06	6
ATOM	618	C	SER	78	10.534	89.350	-19.641	1.00	22.67	6
ATOM	619	O	SER	78	11.580	88.713	-19.501	1.00	31.16	8
ATOM	620	CB	SER	78	9.099	88.675	-17.785	1.00	17.69	6
ATOM	621	OG	SER	78	9.477	89.937	-17.263	1.00	27.32	8

ATOM	622	N	PRO	79	10.494	90.633	-19.974	1.00	14.29	7
ATOM	623	CA	PRO	79	11.673	91.412	-20.326	1.00	11.44	6
ATOM	624	C	PRO	79	12.517	91.680	-19.091	1.00	20.19	6
ATOM	625	O	PRO	79	13.717	91.934	-19.180	1.00	23.63	8
ATOM	626	CB	PRO	79	11.078	92.748	-20.762	1.00	8.46	6
ATOM	627	CG	PRO	79	9.624	92.527	-20.909	1.00	8.26	6
ATOM	628	CD	PRO	79	9.284	91.469	-19.916	1.00	8.04	6
ATOM	629	N	HIS	80	11.865	91.637	-17.936	1.00	18.34	7
ATOM	630	CA	HIS	80	12.532	91.945	-16.677	1.00	19.74	6
ATOM	631	C	HIS	80	13.061	90.804	-15.834	1.00	21.10	6
ATOM	632	O	HIS	80	13.772	91.029	-14.858	1.00	18.50	8
ATOM	633	CB	HIS	80	11.618	92.847	-15.856	1.00	18.31	6
ATOM	634	CG	HIS	80	11.367	94.145	-16.553	1.00	21.86	6
ATOM	635	ND1	HIS	80	10.151	94.463	-17.116	1.00	23.36	7
ATOM	636	CD2	HIS	80	12.227	95.123	-16.921	1.00	22.29	6
ATOM	637	CE1	HIS	80	10.256	95.625	-17.739	1.00	21.91	6
ATOM	638	NE2	HIS	80	11.504	96.047	-17.634	1.00	22.26	7
ATOM	639	N	ALA	81	12.673	89.593	-16.212	1.00	17.20	7
ATOM	640	CA	ALA	81	13.071	88.430	-15.446	1.00	13.31	6
ATOM	641	C	ALA	81	14.580	88.440	-15.265	1.00	18.69	6
ATOM	642	O	ALA	81	15.085	88.072	-14.209	1.00	18.76	8
ATOM	643	CB	ALA	81	12.619	87.177	-16.149	1.00	11.49	6
ATOM	644	N	ALA	82	15.307	88.924	-16.265	1.00	22.59	7
ATOM	645	CA	ALA	82	16.763	88.883	-16.167	1.00	21.51	6
ATOM	646	C	ALA	82	17.352	89.808	-15.115	1.00	20.53	6
ATOM	647	O	ALA	82	18.534	89.714	-14.790	1.00	16.23	8
ATOM	648	CB	ALA	82	17.404	89.097	-17.514	1.00	23.32	6
ATOM	649	N	ARG	83	16.508	90.678	-14.571	1.00	23.78	7
ATOM	650	CA	ARG	83	16.901	91.557	-13.478	1.00	24.97	6
ATOM	651	C	ARG	83	17.303	90.615	-12.342	1.00	33.88	6
ATOM	652	O	ARG	83	18.219	90.891	-11.568	1.00	39.65	8
ATOM	653	CB	ARG	83	15.690	92.388	-13.045	1.00	23.05	6
ATOM	654	CG	ARG	83	15.985	93.629	-12.213	1.00	49.86	6
ATOM	655	CD	ARG	83	16.336	93.329	-10.758	1.00	78.94	6
ATOM	656	NE	ARG	83	16.040	94.455	-9.873	1.00	85.98	7
ATOM	657	CZ	ARG	83	16.606	95.658	-9.951	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	658	NH1	ARG	83	17.502	95.938	-10.888	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	659	NH2	ARG	83	16.237	96.610	-9.102	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	660	N	TRP	84	16.637	89.470	-12.246	1.00	22.21	7
ATOM	661	CA	TRP	84	16.968	88.536	-11.184	1.00	19.43	6
ATOM	662	C	TRP	84	17.755	87.305	-11.608	1.00	31.18	6
ATOM	663	O	TRP	84	17.844	86.342	-10.847	1.00	35.39	8
ATOM	664	CB	TRP	84	15.689	88.085	-10.494	1.00	16.40	6
ATOM	665	CG	TRP	84	15.009	89.219	-9.824	1.00	18.23	6
ATOM	666	CD1	TRP	84	15.187	89.627	-8.540	1.00	21.69	6
ATOM	667	CD2	TRP	84	14.056	90.114	-10.405	1.00	17.07	6
ATOM	668	NE1	TRP	84	14.357	90.687	-8.264	1.00	20.88	7
ATOM	669	CE2	TRP	84	13.669	91.020	-9.401	1.00	19.45	6
ATOM	670	CE3	TRP	84	13.468	90.217	-11.665	1.00	19.59	6
ATOM	671	CZ2	TRP	84	12.725	92.018	-9.612	1.00	18.30	6
ATOM	672	CZ3	TRP	84	12.490	91.171	-11.854	1.00	21.64	6
ATOM	673	CH2	TRP	84	12.121	92.055	-10.835	1.00	21.37	6
ATOM	674	N	ILE	85	18.314	87.322	-12.810	1.00	24.95	7
ATOM	675	CA	ILE	85	19.033	86.156	-13.305	1.00	22.97	6
ATOM	676	C	ILE	85	20.042	85.606	-12.303	1.00	29.57	6
ATOM	677	O	ILE	85	20.670	86.362	-11.564	1.00	30.82	8
ATOM	678	CB	ILE	85	19.782	86.537	-14.585	1.00	23.54	6
ATOM	679	CG1	ILE	85	20.401	85.313	-15.267	1.00	26.18	6
ATOM	680	CG2	ILE	85	20.829	87.552	-14.211	1.00	21.14	6
ATOM	681	CD1	ILE	85	20.633	85.478	-16.762	1.00	24.50	6
ATOM	682	N	ASP	86	20.158	84.283	-12.240	1.00	30.10	7
ATOM	683	CA	ASP	86	21.164	83.677	-11.377	1.00	29.12	6
ATOM	684	C	ASP	86	22.407	83.784	-12.238	1.00	42.28	6

ATOM	685	O	ASP	86	22.491	83.220	-13.330	1.00	39.06	8
ATOM	686	CB	ASP	86	20.918	82.198	-11.066	1.00	30.18	6
ATOM	687	CG	ASP	86	22.080	81.554	-10.313	1.00	44.52	6
ATOM	688	OD1	ASP	86	23.247	81.615	-10.761	1.00	40.19	8
ATOM	689	OD2	ASP	86	21.841	80.950	-9.245	1.00	59.02	8
ATOM	690	N	PRO	87	23.348	84.552	-11.703	1.00	49.48	7
ATOM	691	CA	PRO	87	24.655	84.805	-12.297	1.00	48.64	6
ATOM	692	C	PRO	87	25.402	83.516	-12.602	1.00	46.84	6
ATOM	693	O	PRO	87	26.240	83.472	-13.497	1.00	48.75	8
ATOM	694	CB	PRO	87	25.393	85.524	-11.167	1.00	51.52	6
ATOM	695	CG	PRO	87	24.743	85.003	-9.918	1.00	56.96	6
ATOM	696	CD	PRO	87	23.291	84.940	-10.284	1.00	51.33	6
ATOM	697	N	ARG	88	25.153	82.453	-11.850	1.00	42.19	7
ATOM	698	CA	ARG	88	25.891	81.248	-12.186	1.00	44.89	6
ATOM	699	C	ARG	88	25.142	80.240	-13.050	1.00	49.99	6
ATOM	700	O	ARG	88	25.744	79.321	-13.597	1.00	50.05	8
ATOM	701	CB	ARG	88	26.581	80.623	-10.973	1.00	52.97	6
ATOM	702	CG	ARG	88	25.750	80.527	-9.703	1.00	76.18	6
ATOM	703	CD	ARG	88	26.599	79.861	-8.624	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	704	NE	ARG	88	27.090	78.542	-9.027	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	705	CZ	ARG	88	28.208	78.307	-9.712	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	706	NH1	ARG	88	28.994	79.309	-10.088	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	707	NH2	ARG	88	28.544	77.059	-10.020	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	708	N	TYR	89	23.838	80.434	-13.202	1.00	45.84	7
ATOM	709	CA	TYR	89	23.032	79.541	-14.025	1.00	43.98	6
ATOM	710	C	TYR	89	22.067	80.445	-14.776	1.00	45.45	6
ATOM	711	O	TYR	89	20.960	80.715	-14.312	1.00	45.21	8
ATOM	712	CB	TYR	89	22.264	78.584	-13.121	1.00	48.01	6
ATOM	713	CG	TYR	89	23.177	77.611	-12.419	1.00	61.79	6
ATOM	714	CD1	TYR	89	23.876	77.974	-11.277	1.00	66.20	6
ATOM	715	CD2	TYR	89	23.383	76.336	-12.935	1.00	69.23	6
ATOM	716	CE1	TYR	89	24.730	77.073	-10.656	1.00	74.00	6
ATOM	717	CE2	TYR	89	24.236	75.431	-12.320	1.00	73.13	6
ATOM	718	CZ	TYR	89	24.906	75.802	-11.176	1.00	86.68	6
ATOM	719	OH	TYR	89	25.749	74.887	-10.581	1.00	91.37	8
ATOM	720	N	THR	90	22.524	80.950	-15.916	1.00	37.49	7
ATOM	721	CA	THR	90	21.743	81.914	-16.678	1.00	32.66	6
ATOM	722	C	THR	90	20.387	81.540	-17.244	1.00	27.01	6
ATOM	723	O	THR	90	19.784	82.379	-17.905	1.00	29.89	8
ATOM	724	CB	THR	90	22.560	82.526	-17.804	1.00	28.97	6
ATOM	725	OG1	THR	90	23.151	81.448	-18.539	1.00	34.34	8
ATOM	726	CG2	THR	90	23.652	83.369	-17.196	1.00	35.55	6
ATOM	727	N	ALA	91	19.922	80.311	-17.043	1.00	17.28	7
ATOM	728	CA	ALA	91	18.578	79.961	-17.499	1.00	14.53	6
ATOM	729	C	ALA	91	17.656	80.049	-16.288	1.00	19.62	6
ATOM	730	O	ALA	91	16.436	79.891	-16.384	1.00	15.74	8
ATOM	731	CB	ALA	91	18.534	78.575	-18.082	1.00	13.62	6
ATOM	732	N	ALA	92	18.298	80.367	-15.165	1.00	14.30	7
ATOM	733	CA	ALA	92	17.699	80.489	-13.845	1.00	9.56	6
ATOM	734	C	ALA	92	17.531	81.919	-13.386	1.00	14.17	6
ATOM	735	O	ALA	92	18.340	82.790	-13.689	1.00	16.88	8
ATOM	736	CB	ALA	92	18.591	79.810	-12.831	1.00	9.09	6
ATOM	737	N	ILE	93	16.541	82.100	-12.524	1.00	17.31	7
ATOM	738	CA	ILE	93	16.291	83.389	-11.896	1.00	13.87	6
ATOM	739	C	ILE	93	16.334	83.108	-10.399	1.00	23.42	6
ATOM	740	O	ILE	93	16.178	81.973	-9.948	1.00	22.57	8
ATOM	741	CB	ILE	93	14.909	83.957	-12.258	1.00	12.95	6
ATOM	742	CG1	ILE	93	13.863	82.843	-12.310	1.00	10.29	6
ATOM	743	CG2	ILE	93	14.977	84.680	-13.590	1.00	12.76	6
ATOM	744	CD1	ILE	93	12.537	83.217	-11.684	1.00	17.52	6
ATOM	745	N	GLN	94	16.546	84.158	-9.617	1.00	26.14	7
ATOM	746	CA	GLN	94	16.582	83.965	-8.179	1.00	26.80	6
ATOM	747	C	GLN	94	16.024	85.123	-7.365	1.00	23.51	6

ATOM	748	O	GLN	94	16.362	86.288	-7.574	1.00	24.95	8
ATOM	749	CB	GLN	94	17.982	83.555	-7.720	1.00	30.53	6
ATOM	750	CG	GLN	94	19.076	84.547	-8.063	1.00	86.60	6
ATOM	751	CD	GLN	94	20.446	84.012	-7.706	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	752	OE1	GLN	94	20.563	82.991	-7.027	1.00	91.97	8
ATOM	753	NE2	GLN	94	21.487	84.692	-8.171	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	754	N	SER	95	15.132	84.760	-6.451	1.00	18.46	7
ATOM	755	CA	SER	95	14.536	85.701	-5.516	1.00	20.77	6
ATOM	756	C	SER	95	13.633	86.782	-6.098	1.00	26.96	6
ATOM	757	O	SER	95	13.554	87.901	-5.589	1.00	29.85	8
ATOM	758	CB	SER	95	15.605	86.281	-4.590	1.00	24.66	6
ATOM	759	OG	SER	95	16.213	85.260	-3.814	1.00	49.02	8
ATOM	760	N	VAL	96	12.926	86.443	-7.166	1.00	17.13	7
ATOM	761	CA	VAL	96	12.002	87.409	-7.726	1.00	13.24	6
ATOM	762	C	VAL	96	10.968	87.533	-6.611	1.00	20.61	6
ATOM	763	O	VAL	96	10.559	86.536	-6.017	1.00	20.85	8
ATOM	764	CB	VAL	96	11.387	86.825	-9.000	1.00	14.42	6
ATOM	765	CG1	VAL	96	10.127	87.586	-9.362	1.00	13.32	6
ATOM	766	CG2	VAL	96	12.425	86.842	-10.109	1.00	12.39	6
ATOM	767	N	PRO	97	10.601	88.761	-6.263	1.00	17.13	7
ATOM	768	CA	PRO	97	9.662	88.985	-5.167	1.00	13.86	6
ATOM	769	C	PRO	97	8.203	88.958	-5.600	1.00	20.33	6
ATOM	770	O	PRO	97	7.726	89.897	-6.233	1.00	22.21	8
ATOM	771	CB	PRO	97	9.995	90.409	-4.728	1.00	12.53	6
ATOM	772	CG	PRO	97	10.519	91.050	-5.967	1.00	14.98	6
ATOM	773	CD	PRO	97	11.361	89.980	-6.590	1.00	13.16	6
ATOM	774	N	LEU	98	7.481	87.912	-5.221	1.00	17.90	7
ATOM	775	CA	LEU	98	6.061	87.830	-5.546	1.00	14.49	6
ATOM	776	C	LEU	98	5.172	88.395	-4.436	1.00	13.11	6
ATOM	777	O	LEU	98	5.495	88.351	-3.256	1.00	13.01	8
ATOM	778	CB	LEU	98	5.656	86.390	-5.882	1.00	13.84	6
ATOM	779	CG	LEU	98	6.313	85.625	-7.034	1.00	17.66	6
ATOM	780	CD1	LEU	98	5.872	84.169	-7.048	1.00	12.26	6
ATOM	781	CD2	LEU	98	5.989	86.290	-8.367	1.00	21.18	6
ATOM	782	N	CYS	99	4.010	88.915	-4.797	1.00	8.44	7
ATOM	783	CA	CYS	99	3.119	89.416	-3.772	1.00	9.92	6
ATOM	784	C	CYS	99	2.453	88.235	-3.079	1.00	20.99	6
ATOM	785	O	CYS	99	1.930	87.320	-3.718	1.00	18.24	8
ATOM	786	CB	CYS	99	2.023	90.264	-4.414	1.00	10.56	6
ATOM	787	SG	CYS	99	2.625	91.703	-5.344	1.00	13.73	16
ATOM	788	N	GLN	100	2.399	88.317	-1.756	1.00	22.07	7
ATOM	789	CA	GLN	100	1.770	87.264	-0.977	1.00	21.32	6
ATOM	790	C	GLN	100	0.349	87.055	-1.474	1.00	9.64	6
ATOM	791	O	GLN	100	-0.163	85.940	-1.485	1.00	14.74	8
ATOM	792	CB	GLN	100	1.770	87.631	0.507	1.00	25.92	6
ATOM	793	CG	GLN	100	1.362	86.515	1.455	1.00	42.78	6
ATOM	794	CD	GLN	100	1.274	87.012	2.884	1.00	92.51	6
ATOM	795	OE1	GLN	100	2.293	87.260	3.530	1.00	94.59	8
ATOM	796	NE2	GLN	100	0.052	87.208	3.368	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	797	N	SER	101	-0.296	88.111	-1.947	1.00	8.20	7
ATOM	798	CA	SER	101	-1.656	87.897	-2.441	1.00	10.97	6
ATOM	799	C	SER	101	-1.653	86.937	-3.615	1.00	15.03	6
ATOM	800	O	SER	101	-2.548	86.097	-3.698	1.00	16.14	8
ATOM	801	CB	SER	101	-2.331	89.181	-2.924	1.00	15.42	6
ATOM	802	OG	SER	101	-1.368	90.146	-3.314	1.00	46.89	8
ATOM	803	N	PHE	102	-0.674	87.111	-4.504	1.00	10.62	7
ATOM	804	CA	PHE	102	-0.574	86.313	-5.719	1.00	10.70	6
ATOM	805	C	PHE	102	-0.438	84.884	-5.231	1.00	11.89	6
ATOM	806	O	PHE	102	-1.209	83.985	-5.581	1.00	10.79	8
ATOM	807	CB	PHE	102	0.637	86.691	-6.577	1.00	15.26	6
ATOM	808	CG	PHE	102	0.775	85.854	-7.822	1.00	20.92	6
ATOM	809	CD1	PHE	102	-0.124	85.980	-8.866	1.00	25.44	6
ATOM	810	CD2	PHE	102	1.739	84.863	-7.911	1.00	28.30	6

ATOM	811	CE1	PHE	102	-0.040	85.168	-9.982	1.00	27.38	6
ATOM	812	CE2	PHE	102	1.834	84.054	-9.033	1.00	30.63	6
ATOM	813	CZ	PHE	102	0.941	84.206	-10.070	1.00	28.08	6
ATOM	814	N	CYS	103	0.519	84.722	-4.331	1.00	5.34	7
ATOM	815	CA	CYS	103	0.728	83.391	-3.795	1.00	7.25	6
ATOM	816	C	CYS	103	-0.524	82.795	-3.167	1.00	18.23	6
ATOM	817	O	CYS	103	-0.910	81.670	-3.481	1.00	22.48	8
ATOM	818	CB	CYS	103	1.894	83.452	-2.821	1.00	7.88	6
ATOM	819	SG	CYS	103	3.375	83.846	-3.802	1.00	14.15	16
ATOM	820	N	ASP	104	-1.177	83.553	-2.296	1.00	15.06	7
ATOM	821	CA	ASP	104	-2.350	83.027	-1.612	1.00	19.05	6
ATOM	822	C	ASP	104	-3.435	82.669	-2.623	1.00	21.99	6
ATOM	823	O	ASP	104	-4.150	81.672	-2.493	1.00	21.71	8
ATOM	824	CB	ASP	104	-2.884	84.066	-0.623	1.00	24.73	6
ATOM	825	CG	ASP	104	-1.920	84.364	0.517	1.00	40.08	6
ATOM	826	OD1	ASP	104	-1.189	83.445	0.943	1.00	42.92	8
ATOM	827	OD2	ASP	104	-1.929	85.506	1.026	1.00	47.19	8
ATOM	828	N	ASP	105	-3.537	83.520	-3.637	1.00	16.46	7
ATOM	829	CA	ASP	105	-4.538	83.357	-4.680	1.00	20.61	6
ATOM	830	C	ASP	105	-4.296	82.080	-5.470	1.00	20.03	6
ATOM	831	O	ASP	105	-5.201	81.287	-5.735	1.00	21.62	8
ATOM	832	CB	ASP	105	-4.430	84.539	-5.643	1.00	25.78	6
ATOM	833	CG	ASP	105	-5.257	85.726	-5.202	1.00	42.92	6
ATOM	834	OD1	ASP	105	-5.814	85.675	-4.082	1.00	40.66	8
ATOM	835	OD2	ASP	105	-5.330	86.696	-5.986	1.00	61.10	8
ATOM	836	N	TRP	106	-3.042	81.951	-5.881	1.00	8.21	7
ATOM	837	CA	TRP	106	-2.559	80.810	-6.631	1.00	8.28	6
ATOM	838	C	TRP	106	-2.816	79.533	-5.837	1.00	11.60	6
ATOM	839	O	TRP	106	-3.337	78.552	-6.368	1.00	15.16	8
ATOM	840	CB	TRP	106	-1.064	81.041	-6.844	1.00	5.54	6
ATOM	841	CG	TRP	106	-0.404	80.027	-7.699	1.00	6.08	6
ATOM	842	CD1	TRP	106	-0.991	78.972	-8.340	1.00	8.98	6
ATOM	843	CD2	TRP	106	1.001	79.932	-7.955	1.00	5.84	6
ATOM	844	NE1	TRP	106	-0.027	78.221	-8.972	1.00	7.83	7
ATOM	845	CE2	TRP	106	1.201	78.788	-8.751	1.00	6.14	6
ATOM	846	CE3	TRP	106	2.108	80.697	-7.579	1.00	9.43	6
ATOM	847	CZ2	TRP	106	2.466	78.401	-9.189	1.00	4.81	6
ATOM	848	CZ3	TRP	106	3.368	80.285	-7.982	1.00	10.59	6
ATOM	849	CH2	TRP	106	3.537	79.146	-8.778	1.00	9.52	6
ATOM	850	N	TYR	107	-2.487	79.576	-4.551	1.00	6.27	7
ATOM	851	CA	TYR	107	-2.643	78.433	-3.654	1.00	9.04	6
ATOM	852	C	TYR	107	-4.109	78.058	-3.597	1.00	9.27	6
ATOM	853	O	TYR	107	-4.501	76.895	-3.649	1.00	7.96	8
ATOM	854	CB	TYR	107	-2.209	78.794	-2.230	1.00	12.22	6
ATOM	855	CG	TYR	107	-2.322	77.651	-1.244	1.00	15.49	6
ATOM	856	CD1	TYR	107	-1.287	76.737	-1.074	1.00	15.98	6
ATOM	857	CD2	TYR	107	-3.470	77.469	-0.488	1.00	17.97	6
ATOM	858	CE1	TYR	107	-1.393	75.666	-0.200	1.00	11.73	6
ATOM	859	CE2	TYR	107	-3.580	76.409	0.399	1.00	18.73	6
ATOM	860	CZ	TYR	107	-2.540	75.515	0.549	1.00	28.41	6
ATOM	861	OH	TYR	107	-2.659	74.488	1.464	1.00	29.07	8
ATOM	862	N	GLU	108	-4.922	79.088	-3.441	1.00	8.08	7
ATOM	863	CA	GLU	108	-6.346	78.822	-3.377	1.00	14.08	6
ATOM	864	C	GLU	108	-6.819	78.089	-4.623	1.00	15.89	6
ATOM	865	O	GLU	108	-7.626	77.161	-4.536	1.00	13.96	8
ATOM	866	CB	GLU	108	-7.113	80.134	-3.226	1.00	19.42	6
ATOM	867	CG	GLU	108	-7.103	80.640	-1.792	1.00	69.39	6
ATOM	868	CD	GLU	108	-7.746	79.657	-0.835	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	869	OE1	GLU	108	-7.156	79.415	0.240	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	870	OE2	GLU	108	-8.829	79.129	-1.174	1.00	70.38	8
ATOM	871	N	ALA	109	-6.335	78.547	-5.775	1.00	14.00	7
ATOM	872	CA	ALA	109	-6.706	78.001	-7.081	1.00	12.22	6
ATOM	873	C	ALA	109	-6.334	76.533	-7.265	1.00	17.79	6

ATOM	874	O	ALA	109	-7.126	75.727	-7.757	1.00	18.47	8
ATOM	875	CB	ALA	109	-6.046	78.817	-8.172	1.00	13.29	6
ATOM	876	N	CYS	110	-5.122	76.197	-6.834	1.00	9.54	7
ATOM	877	CA	CYS	110	-4.623	74.842	-6.958	1.00	8.56	6
ATOM	878	C	CYS	110	-4.902	73.942	-5.763	1.00	14.10	6
ATOM	879	O	CYS	110	-4.567	72.758	-5.798	1.00	9.63	8
ATOM	880	CB	CYS	110	-3.120	74.935	-7.206	1.00	8.45	6
ATOM	881	SG	CYS	110	-2.765	75.920	-8.697	1.00	11.66	16
ATOM	882	N	LYS	111	-5.452	74.517	-4.698	1.00	17.19	7
ATOM	883	CA	LYS	111	-5.627	73.785	-3.447	1.00	18.55	6
ATOM	884	C	LYS	111	-6.168	72.377	-3.618	1.00	11.33	6
ATOM	885	O	LYS	111	-5.661	71.410	-3.059	1.00	10.00	8
ATOM	886	CB	LYS	111	-6.408	74.568	-2.384	1.00	22.65	6
ATOM	887	CG	LYS	111	-7.875	74.817	-2.713	1.00	47.50	6
ATOM	888	CD	LYS	111	-8.699	75.239	-1.498	1.00	40.57	6
ATOM	889	CE	LYS	111	-7.885	76.127	-0.564	1.00	89.80	6
ATOM	890	NZ	LYS	111	-8.096	75.886	0.897	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	891	N	ASP	112	-7.169	72.228	-4.466	1.00	11.84	7
ATOM	892	CA	ASP	112	-7.689	70.880	-4.586	1.00	11.97	6
ATOM	893	C	ASP	112	-7.067	70.089	-5.720	1.00	19.05	6
ATOM	894	O	ASP	112	-7.458	68.949	-5.954	1.00	21.15	8
ATOM	895	CB	ASP	112	-9.211	70.898	-4.656	1.00	15.06	6
ATOM	896	CG	ASP	112	-9.818	71.354	-3.350	1.00	36.45	6
ATOM	897	OD1	ASP	112	-10.851	72.056	-3.359	1.00	43.86	8
ATOM	898	OD2	ASP	112	-9.177	71.048	-2.323	1.00	35.06	8
ATOM	899	N	ASP	113	-6.100	70.679	-6.412	1.00	15.66	7
ATOM	900	CA	ASP	113	-5.436	69.932	-7.473	1.00	12.63	6
ATOM	901	C	ASP	113	-4.333	69.096	-6.844	1.00	19.00	6
ATOM	902	O	ASP	113	-4.045	69.217	-5.651	1.00	21.71	8
ATOM	903	CB	ASP	113	-4.881	70.834	-8.574	1.00	12.21	6
ATOM	904	CG	ASP	113	-5.979	71.412	-9.442	1.00	13.70	6
ATOM	905	OD1	ASP	113	-6.309	72.606	-9.278	1.00	13.94	8
ATOM	906	OD2	ASP	113	-6.552	70.648	-10.245	1.00	32.13	8
ATOM	907	N	SER	114	-3.755	68.232	-7.670	1.00	11.63	7
ATOM	908	CA	SER	114	-2.707	67.324	-7.227	1.00	8.29	6
ATOM	909	C	SER	114	-1.368	67.582	-7.892	1.00	12.59	6
ATOM	910	O	SER	114	-1.308	68.112	-9.000	1.00	16.81	8
ATOM	911	CB	SER	114	-3.161	65.885	-7.402	1.00	10.61	6
ATOM	912	OG	SER	114	-4.298	65.714	-6.572	1.00	37.38	8
ATOM	913	N	ILE	115	-0.308	67.254	-7.165	1.00	5.50	7
ATOM	914	CA	ILE	115	1.049	67.568	-7.581	1.00	3.44	6
ATOM	915	C	ILE	115	1.897	66.474	-6.953	1.00	9.21	6
ATOM	916	O	ILE	115	1.461	65.879	-5.968	1.00	9.04	8
ATOM	917	CB	ILE	115	1.402	68.962	-7.027	1.00	3.89	6
ATOM	918	CG1	ILE	115	2.791	69.438	-7.440	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	919	CG2	ILE	115	1.274	68.974	-5.520	1.00	8.31	6
ATOM	920	CD1	ILE	115	2.897	70.938	-7.523	1.00	9.23	6
ATOM	921	N	CYS	116	3.027	66.134	-7.569	1.00	4.08	7
ATOM	922	CA	CYS	116	3.858	65.055	-7.044	1.00	1.68	6
ATOM	923	C	CYS	116	5.298	65.536	-7.014	1.00	6.31	6
ATOM	924	O	CYS	116	6.222	64.730	-6.913	1.00	15.31	8
ATOM	925	CB	CYS	116	3.763	63.819	-7.936	1.00	2.27	6
ATOM	926	SG	CYS	116	4.559	64.206	-9.525	1.00	8.86	16
ATOM	927	N	ALA	117	5.492	66.842	-7.156	1.00	1.51	7
ATOM	928	CA	ALA	117	6.838	67.404	-7.146	1.00	2.52	6
ATOM	929	C	ALA	117	6.781	68.655	-6.296	1.00	11.15	6
ATOM	930	O	ALA	117	6.103	69.614	-6.664	1.00	13.88	8
ATOM	931	CB	ALA	117	7.324	67.741	-8.553	1.00	2.54	6
ATOM	932	N	HIS	118	7.458	68.617	-5.154	1.00	10.41	7
ATOM	933	CA	HIS	118	7.446	69.756	-4.245	1.00	11.11	6
ATOM	934	C	HIS	118	8.243	70.916	-4.853	1.00	13.42	6
ATOM	935	O	HIS	118	7.855	72.082	-4.763	1.00	14.30	8
ATOM	936	CB	HIS	118	8.009	69.297	-2.878	1.00	10.69	6

ATOM	937	CG	HIS	118	7.918	70.317	-1.785	1.00	11.29	6
ATOM	938	ND1	HIS	118	8.985	71.115	-1.432	1.00	9.20	7
ATOM	939	CD2	HIS	118	6.938	70.583	-0.887	1.00	11.04	6
ATOM	940	CE1	HIS	118	8.640	71.881	-0.413	1.00	7.39	6
ATOM	941	NE2	HIS	118	7.405	71.576	-0.058	1.00	9.57	7
ATOM	942	N	ASN	119	9.374	70.587	-5.471	1.00	6.70	7
ATOM	943	CA	ASN	119	10.239	71.575	-6.105	1.00	6.12	6
ATOM	944	C	ASN	119	10.353	71.101	-7.542	1.00	15.44	6
ATOM	945	O	ASN	119	10.941	70.051	-7.795	1.00	12.28	8
ATOM	946	CB	ASN	119	11.642	71.546	-5.505	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	947	CG	ASN	119	12.608	72.483	-6.213	1.00	19.41	6
ATOM	948	OD1	ASN	119	12.571	72.666	-7.429	1.00	22.58	8
ATOM	949	ND2	ASN	119	13.502	73.082	-5.440	1.00	15.73	7
ATOM	950	N	TRP	120	9.837	71.888	-8.478	1.00	15.93	7
ATOM	951	CA	TRP	120	9.894	71.475	-9.870	1.00	15.00	6
ATOM	952	C	TRP	120	11.253	71.486	-10.551	1.00	23.59	6
ATOM	953	O	TRP	120	11.409	70.952	-11.643	1.00	29.56	8
ATOM	954	CB	TRP	120	8.929	72.324	-10.675	1.00	12.57	6
ATOM	955	CG	TRP	120	7.534	71.850	-10.485	1.00	12.54	6
ATOM	956	CD1	TRP	120	6.918	71.573	-9.305	1.00	14.86	6
ATOM	957	CD2	TRP	120	6.571	71.627	-11.516	1.00	10.89	6
ATOM	958	NE1	TRP	120	5.622	71.185	-9.541	1.00	15.27	7
ATOM	959	CE2	TRP	120	5.377	71.240	-10.889	1.00	14.57	6
ATOM	960	CE3	TRP	120	6.604	71.722	-12.908	1.00	11.47	6
ATOM	961	CZ2	TRP	120	4.227	70.943	-11.603	1.00	12.79	6
ATOM	962	CZ3	TRP	120	5.469	71.419	-13.618	1.00	11.25	6
ATOM	963	CH2	TRP	120	4.289	71.066	-12.961	1.00	12.54	6
ATOM	964	N	LEU	121	12.228	72.146	-9.943	1.00	19.90	7
ATOM	965	CA	LEU	121	13.547	72.169	-10.552	1.00	17.37	6
ATOM	966	C	LEU	121	14.333	70.976	-10.034	1.00	20.93	6
ATOM	967	O	LEU	121	15.451	70.721	-10.473	1.00	27.70	8
ATOM	968	CB	LEU	121	14.278	73.451	-10.158	1.00	16.15	6
ATOM	969	CG	LEU	121	13.382	74.587	-10.634	1.00	20.85	6
ATOM	970	CD1	LEU	121	13.654	75.722	-9.677	1.00	25.36	6
ATOM	971	CD2	LEU	121	13.685	74.920	-12.084	1.00	12.16	6
ATOM	972	N	THR	122	13.778	70.234	-9.086	1.00	13.38	7
ATOM	973	CA	THR	122	14.585	69.145	-8.555	1.00	14.14	6
ATOM	974	C	THR	122	13.890	67.801	-8.390	1.00	19.85	6
ATOM	975	O	THR	122	14.483	66.736	-8.543	1.00	23.83	8
ATOM	976	CB	THR	122	15.171	69.561	-7.189	1.00	18.99	6
ATOM	977	OG1	THR	122	14.108	69.845	-6.273	1.00	25.47	8
ATOM	978	CG2	THR	122	15.991	70.823	-7.339	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	979	N	ASP	123	12.610	67.851	-8.057	1.00	17.18	7
ATOM	980	CA	ASP	123	11.896	66.640	-7.712	1.00	13.91	6
ATOM	981	C	ASP	123	11.320	65.820	-8.840	1.00	11.37	6
ATOM	982	O	ASP	123	10.528	64.911	-8.607	1.00	23.93	8
ATOM	983	CB	ASP	123	10.875	66.976	-6.627	1.00	17.22	6
ATOM	984	CG	ASP	123	11.514	67.726	-5.476	1.00	16.86	6
ATOM	985	OD1	ASP	123	12.763	67.780	-5.476	1.00	17.98	8
ATOM	986	OD2	ASP	123	10.798	68.239	-4.591	1.00	34.81	8
ATOM	987	N	TRP	124	11.724	66.116	-10.066	1.00	7.33	7
ATOM	988	CA	TRP	124	11.220	65.308	-11.173	1.00	10.28	6
ATOM	989	C	TRP	124	12.267	64.295	-11.620	1.00	19.91	6
ATOM	990	O	TRP	124	13.462	64.577	-11.577	1.00	25.29	8
ATOM	991	CB	TRP	124	10.959	66.180	-12.404	1.00	5.58	6
ATOM	992	CG	TRP	124	9.754	67.055	-12.338	1.00	3.52	6
ATOM	993	CD1	TRP	124	9.733	68.413	-12.243	1.00	5.63	6
ATOM	994	CD2	TRP	124	8.388	66.633	-12.364	1.00	1.69	6
ATOM	995	NE1	TRP	124	8.436	68.871	-12.248	1.00	6.71	7
ATOM	996	CE2	TRP	124	7.592	67.796	-12.325	1.00	4.44	6
ATOM	997	CE3	TRP	124	7.767	65.385	-12.442	1.00	1.89	6
ATOM	998	CZ2	TRP	124	6.207	67.757	-12.409	1.00	2.54	6
ATOM	999	CZ3	TRP	124	6.382	65.344	-12.488	1.00	3.77	6

ATOM	1000	CH2	TRP	124	5.622	66.522	-12.507	1.00	4.65	6
ATOM	1001	N	GLU	125	11.810	63.163	-12.145	1.00	10.73	7
ATOM	1002	CA	GLU	125	12.711	62.229	-12.798	1.00	11.22	6
ATOM	1003	C	GLU	125	12.559	62.594	-14.275	1.00	20.09	6
ATOM	1004	O	GLU	125	11.451	62.555	-14.814	1.00	20.56	8
ATOM	1005	CB	GLU	125	12.189	60.803	-12.636	1.00	13.46	6
ATOM	1006	CG	GLU	125	12.935	59.774	-13.477	1.00	15.14	6
ATOM	1007	CD	GLU	125	14.126	59.193	-12.735	1.00	84.82	6
ATOM	1008	OE1	GLU	125	14.190	57.950	-12.640	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1009	OE2	GLU	125	14.977	59.969	-12.242	1.00	73.65	8
ATOM	1010	N	ARG	126	13.639	62.984	-14.942	1.00	19.85	7
ATOM	1011	CA	ARG	126	13.505	63.304	-16.362	1.00	19.51	6
ATOM	1012	C	ARG	126	14.165	62.276	-17.266	1.00	19.91	6
ATOM	1013	O	ARG	126	15.353	62.002	-17.142	1.00	27.30	8
ATOM	1014	CB	ARG	126	13.941	64.731	-16.705	1.00	11.25	6
ATOM	1015	CG	ARG	126	13.280	65.722	-15.769	1.00	26.34	6
ATOM	1016	CD	ARG	126	13.232	67.125	-16.321	1.00	5.55	6
ATOM	1017	NE	ARG	126	12.095	67.311	-17.216	1.00	27.05	7
ATOM	1018	CZ	ARG	126	11.208	68.292	-17.092	1.00	16.69	6
ATOM	1019	NH1	ARG	126	11.309	69.159	-16.092	1.00	6.55	7
ATOM	1020	NH2	ARG	126	10.238	68.414	-17.988	1.00	44.57	7
ATOM	1021	N	ASP	127	13.395	61.693	-18.175	1.00	13.12	7
ATOM	1022	CA	ASP	127	13.967	60.662	-19.024	1.00	13.81	6
ATOM	1023	C	ASP	127	14.934	61.088	-20.125	1.00	34.50	6
ATOM	1024	O	ASP	127	15.404	62.227	-20.209	1.00	30.50	8
ATOM	1025	CB	ASP	127	12.892	59.721	-19.569	1.00	7.89	6
ATOM	1026	CG	ASP	127	12.026	60.385	-20.609	1.00	28.30	6
ATOM	1027	OD1	ASP	127	12.439	61.416	-21.187	1.00	30.51	8
ATOM	1028	OD2	ASP	127	10.915	59.858	-20.823	1.00	35.04	8
ATOM	1029	N	GLU	128	15.194	60.102	-20.972	1.00	44.16	7
ATOM	1030	CA	GLU	128	16.079	60.229	-22.119	1.00	50.40	6
ATOM	1031	C	GLU	128	15.628	61.401	-22.986	1.00	55.14	6
ATOM	1032	O	GLU	128	16.448	62.209	-23.426	1.00	60.22	8
ATOM	1033	CB	GLU	128	16.025	58.927	-22.923	1.00	54.76	6
ATOM	1034	CG	GLU	128	15.947	57.650	-22.085	1.00	81.23	6
ATOM	1035	CD	GLU	128	14.531	57.130	-21.883	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1036	OE1	GLU	128	13.587	57.696	-22.478	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1037	OE2	GLU	128	14.358	56.146	-21.130	1.00	67.89	8
ATOM	1038	N	SER	129	14.322	61.493	-23.220	1.00	39.73	7
ATOM	1039	CA	SER	129	13.783	62.576	-24.031	1.00	32.94	6
ATOM	1040	C	SER	129	13.544	63.857	-23.246	1.00	36.32	6
ATOM	1041	O	SER	129	13.005	64.809	-23.801	1.00	38.23	8
ATOM	1042	CB	SER	129	12.466	62.152	-24.665	1.00	36.15	6
ATOM	1043	OG	SER	129	11.536	61.820	-23.651	1.00	66.73	8
ATOM	1044	N	GLY	130	13.906	63.890	-21.967	1.00	32.94	7
ATOM	1045	CA	GLY	130	13.707	65.093	-21.165	1.00	30.48	6
ATOM	1046	C	GLY	130	12.280	65.174	-20.633	1.00	25.57	6
ATOM	1047	O	GLY	130	11.910	66.114	-19.931	1.00	23.90	8
ATOM	1048	N	GLU	131	11.480	64.185	-21.013	1.00	17.42	7
ATOM	1049	CA	GLU	131	10.097	64.093	-20.574	1.00	20.84	6
ATOM	1050	C	GLU	131	10.213	63.941	-19.060	1.00	21.78	6
ATOM	1051	O	GLU	131	11.196	63.388	-18.576	1.00	21.39	8
ATOM	1052	CB	GLU	131	9.521	62.813	-21.179	1.00	26.27	6
ATOM	1053	CG	GLU	131	8.169	62.916	-21.865	1.00	45.55	6
ATOM	1054	CD	GLU	131	8.246	63.623	-23.204	1.00	59.09	6
ATOM	1055	OE1	GLU	131	7.574	63.150	-24.144	1.00	58.98	8
ATOM	1056	OE2	GLU	131	8.939	64.660	-23.299	1.00	46.04	8
ATOM	1057	N	ASN	132	9.235	64.433	-18.306	1.00	17.35	7
ATOM	1058	CA	ASN	132	9.292	64.390	-16.846	1.00	16.16	6
ATOM	1059	C	ASN	132	8.331	63.421	-16.171	1.00	12.70	6
ATOM	1060	O	ASN	132	7.181	63.265	-16.575	1.00	8.55	8
ATOM	1061	CB	ASN	132	8.995	65.776	-16.280	1.00	12.92	6
ATOM	1062	CG	ASN	132	7.568	66.215	-16.552	1.00	12.67	6

ATOM	1063	OD1	ASN	132	6.859	66.618	-15.634	1.00	14.84	8
ATOM	1064	ND2	ASN	132	7.145	66.174	-17.812	1.00	4.42	7
ATOM	1065	N	HIS	133	8.793	62.809	-15.089	1.00	14.02	7
ATOM	1066	CA	HIS	133	7.950	61.868	-14.363	1.00	16.12	6
ATOM	1067	C	HIS	133	8.074	62.033	-12.858	1.00	20.96	6
ATOM	1068	O	HIS	133	9.144	62.411	-12.373	1.00	19.78	8
ATOM	1069	CB	HIS	133	8.419	60.456	-14.669	1.00	18.77	6
ATOM	1070	CG	HIS	133	8.337	60.106	-16.119	1.00	25.29	6
ATOM	1071	ND1	HIS	133	9.340	60.417	-17.013	1.00	26.84	7
ATOM	1072	CD2	HIS	133	7.373	59.472	-16.827	1.00	28.19	6
ATOM	1073	CE1	HIS	133	8.999	59.981	-18.213	1.00	26.54	6
ATOM	1074	NE2	HIS	133	7.815	59.401	-18.125	1.00	27.66	7
ATOM	1075	N	CYS	134	6.994	61.681	-12.160	1.00	12.58	7
ATOM	1076	CA	CYS	134	6.922	61.756	-10.704	1.00	6.92	6
ATOM	1077	C	CYS	134	7.797	60.692	-10.058	1.00	11.13	6
ATOM	1078	O	CYS	134	7.836	59.550	-10.518	1.00	9.50	8
ATOM	1079	CB	CYS	134	5.516	61.429	-10.207	1.00	5.38	6
ATOM	1080	SG	CYS	134	4.146	62.550	-10.616	1.00	8.07	16
ATOM	1081	N	LYS	135	8.434	61.059	-8.950	1.00	14.27	7
ATOM	1082	CA	LYS	135	9.190	60.112	-8.137	1.00	12.16	6
ATOM	1083	C	LYS	135	8.307	59.873	-6.903	1.00	11.32	6
ATOM	1084	O	LYS	135	7.941	58.763	-6.519	1.00	17.31	8
ATOM	1085	CB	LYS	135	10.544	60.722	-7.777	1.00	14.13	6
ATOM	1086	CG	LYS	135	11.695	60.440	-8.739	1.00	14.85	6
ATOM	1087	CD	LYS	135	12.934	61.229	-8.322	1.00	16.53	6
ATOM	1088	CE	LYS	135	14.182	60.884	-9.120	1.00	42.09	6
ATOM	1089	NZ	LYS	135	15.057	62.066	-9.417	1.00	62.71	7
ATOM	1090	N	SER	136	7.795	60.981	-6.396	1.00	2.16	7
ATOM	1091	CA	SER	136	6.931	61.007	-5.237	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	1092	C	SER	136	5.456	60.902	-5.569	1.00	12.40	6
ATOM	1093	O	SER	136	4.972	61.315	-6.622	1.00	19.44	8
ATOM	1094	CB	SER	136	7.171	62.319	-4.491	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	1095	OG	SER	136	8.561	62.552	-4.309	1.00	35.40	8
ATOM	1096	N	LYS	137	4.735	60.405	-4.576	1.00	12.54	7
ATOM	1097	CA	LYS	137	3.301	60.221	-4.662	1.00	11.65	6
ATOM	1098	C	LYS	137	2.612	61.522	-5.065	1.00	12.33	6
ATOM	1099	O	LYS	137	3.091	62.615	-4.779	1.00	10.82	8
ATOM	1100	CB	LYS	137	2.838	59.786	-3.272	1.00	12.40	6
ATOM	1101	CG	LYS	137	2.093	58.462	-3.242	1.00	15.93	6
ATOM	1102	CD	LYS	137	2.982	57.266	-3.486	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	1103	CE	LYS	137	2.150	56.095	-4.003	1.00	8.42	6
ATOM	1104	NZ	LYS	137	1.036	55.730	-3.085	1.00	52.83	7
ATOM	1105	N	CYS	138	1.453	61.412	-5.700	1.00	11.38	7
ATOM	1106	CA	CYS	138	0.702	62.614	-6.040	1.00	10.71	6
ATOM	1107	C	CYS	138	-0.176	62.895	-4.828	1.00	14.37	6
ATOM	1108	O	CYS	138	-0.877	62.011	-4.330	1.00	14.21	8
ATOM	1109	CB	CYS	138	-0.249	62.331	-7.210	1.00	12.14	6
ATOM	1110	SG	CYS	138	0.452	62.086	-8.879	1.00	12.76	16
ATOM	1111	N	VAL	139	-0.180	64.149	-4.395	1.00	13.51	7
ATOM	1112	CA	VAL	139	-1.001	64.589	-3.276	1.00	9.48	6
ATOM	1113	C	VAL	139	-1.579	65.941	-3.673	1.00	11.81	6
ATOM	1114	O	VAL	139	-1.063	66.605	-4.570	1.00	14.31	8
ATOM	1115	CB	VAL	139	-0.155	64.802	-2.007	1.00	12.59	6
ATOM	1116	CG1	VAL	139	0.896	65.876	-2.222	1.00	11.01	6
ATOM	1117	CG2	VAL	139	0.443	63.499	-1.509	1.00	14.59	6
ATOM	1118	N	PRO	140	-2.621	66.357	-2.966	1.00	4.09	7
ATOM	1119	CA	PRO	140	-3.268	67.636	-3.207	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	1120	C	PRO	140	-2.229	68.684	-2.902	1.00	8.25	6
ATOM	1121	O	PRO	140	-1.302	68.456	-2.130	1.00	13.53	8
ATOM	1122	CB	PRO	140	-4.289	67.729	-2.079	1.00	1.00	6
ATOM	1123	CG	PRO	140	-4.612	66.328	-1.778	1.00	4.85	6
ATOM	1124	CD	PRO	140	-3.324	65.576	-1.937	1.00	7.18	6
ATOM	1125	N	TYR	141	-2.440	69.849	-3.496	1.00	7.82	7

ATOM	1126	CA	TYR	141	-1.514	70.948	-3.303	1.00	8.47	6
ATOM	1127	C	TYR	141	-1.567	71.317	-1.822	1.00	15.55	6
ATOM	1128	O	TYR	141	-0.557	71.646	-1.196	1.00	14.81	8
ATOM	1129	CB	TYR	141	-1.989	72.118	-4.166	1.00	8.60	6
ATOM	1130	CG	TYR	141	-1.407	72.193	-5.564	1.00	9.89	6
ATOM	1131	CD1	TYR	141	-1.745	71.272	-6.551	1.00	9.52	6
ATOM	1132	CD2	TYR	141	-0.589	73.260	-5.919	1.00	10.71	6
ATOM	1133	CE1	TYR	141	-1.259	71.395	-7.846	1.00	3.65	6
ATOM	1134	CE2	TYR	141	-0.100	73.391	-7.204	1.00	10.69	6
ATOM	1135	CZ	TYR	141	-0.444	72.463	-8.162	1.00	9.18	6
ATOM	1136	OH	TYR	141	0.114	72.625	-9.406	1.00	21.60	8
ATOM	1137	N	SER	142	-2.773	71.255	-1.269	1.00	11.14	7
ATOM	1138	CA	SER	142	-3.006	71.649	0.118	1.00	10.71	6
ATOM	1139	C	SER	142	-2.316	70.733	1.118	1.00	19.88	6
ATOM	1140	O	SER	142	-2.157	71.069	2.289	1.00	22.47	8
ATOM	1141	CB	SER	142	-4.502	71.667	0.409	1.00	10.04	6
ATOM	1142	OG	SER	142	-5.025	70.364	0.227	1.00	20.49	8
ATOM	1143	N	GLU	143	-1.890	69.572	0.638	1.00	18.50	7
ATOM	1144	CA	GLU	143	-1.134	68.661	1.481	1.00	16.05	6
ATOM	1145	C	GLU	143	0.359	68.788	1.198	1.00	16.70	6
ATOM	1146	O	GLU	143	1.173	68.505	2.073	1.00	18.59	8
ATOM	1147	CB	GLU	143	-1.628	67.224	1.313	1.00	17.70	6
ATOM	1148	CG	GLU	143	-3.043	67.034	1.859	1.00	36.48	6
ATOM	1149	CD	GLU	143	-3.143	66.786	3.357	1.00	19.74	6
ATOM	1150	OE1	GLU	143	-2.406	67.399	4.162	1.00	34.68	8
ATOM	1151	OE2	GLU	143	-3.957	65.922	3.745	1.00	50.13	8
ATOM	1152	N	MET	144	0.732	69.247	0.006	1.00	8.49	7
ATOM	1153	CA	MET	144	2.141	69.368	-0.339	1.00	2.71	6
ATOM	1154	C	MET	144	2.706	70.673	0.191	1.00	4.12	6
ATOM	1155	O	MET	144	3.911	70.818	0.387	1.00	7.53	8
ATOM	1156	CB	MET	144	2.288	69.371	-1.856	1.00	5.30	6
ATOM	1157	CG	MET	144	3.684	69.715	-2.336	1.00	8.07	6
ATOM	1158	SD	MET	144	4.711	68.229	-2.345	1.00	15.03	16
ATOM	1159	CE	MET	144	3.878	67.231	-3.549	1.00	11.06	6
ATOM	1160	N	TYR	145	1.832	71.658	0.341	1.00	3.34	7
ATOM	1161	CA	TYR	145	2.278	72.963	0.803	1.00	2.44	6
ATOM	1162	C	TYR	145	1.391	73.459	1.927	1.00	11.65	6
ATOM	1163	O	TYR	145	0.172	73.307	1.939	1.00	15.16	8
ATOM	1164	CB	TYR	145	2.194	73.985	-0.325	1.00	5.90	6
ATOM	1165	CG	TYR	145	2.982	73.583	-1.548	1.00	9.55	6
ATOM	1166	CD1	TYR	145	2.335	73.203	-2.717	1.00	12.46	6
ATOM	1167	CD2	TYR	145	4.368	73.512	-1.505	1.00	6.81	6
ATOM	1168	CE1	TYR	145	3.051	72.880	-3.851	1.00	11.81	6
ATOM	1169	CE2	TYR	145	5.090	73.125	-2.614	1.00	6.40	6
ATOM	1170	CZ	TYR	145	4.423	72.825	-3.782	1.00	12.12	6
ATOM	1171	OH	TYR	145	5.131	72.433	-4.889	1.00	13.50	8
ATOM	1172	N	ALA	146	2.047	74.113	2.868	1.00	9.73	7
ATOM	1173	CA	ALA	146	1.359	74.632	4.035	1.00	9.21	6
ATOM	1174	C	ALA	146	0.414	75.753	3.650	1.00	18.02	6
ATOM	1175	O	ALA	146	-0.641	75.934	4.255	1.00	18.26	8
ATOM	1176	CB	ALA	146	2.403	75.189	4.964	1.00	9.94	6
ATOM	1177	N	ASN	147	0.845	76.535	2.669	1.00	16.00	7
ATOM	1178	CA	ASN	147	0.076	77.708	2.297	1.00	13.91	6
ATOM	1179	C	ASN	147	0.802	78.285	1.089	1.00	14.15	6
ATOM	1180	O	ASN	147	1.863	77.793	0.703	1.00	12.56	8
ATOM	1181	CB	ASN	147	0.116	78.683	3.482	1.00	14.39	6
ATOM	1182	CG	ASN	147	1.531	78.991	3.946	1.00	36.33	6
ATOM	1183	OD1	ASN	147	2.446	79.100	3.129	1.00	26.80	8
ATOM	1184	ND2	ASN	147	1.724	79.123	5.258	1.00	42.69	7
ATOM	1185	N	GLY	148	0.243	79.367	0.559	1.00	15.09	7
ATOM	1186	CA	GLY	148	0.751	80.034	-0.632	1.00	13.99	6
ATOM	1187	C	GLY	148	2.202	80.442	-0.452	1.00	17.77	6
ATOM	1188	O	GLY	148	3.010	80.377	-1.382	1.00	20.05	8

ATOM	1189	N	THR	149	2.523	80.867	0.764	1.00	10.91	7
ATOM	1190	CA	THR	149	3.878	81.326	1.016	1.00	7.36	6
ATOM	1191	C	THR	149	4.798	80.126	0.901	1.00	13.11	6
ATOM	1192	O	THR	149	5.831	80.189	0.234	1.00	12.21	8
ATOM	1193	CB	THR	149	3.993	81.990	2.389	1.00	19.77	6
ATOM	1194	OG1	THR	149	3.021	83.043	2.488	1.00	19.03	8
ATOM	1195	CG2	THR	149	5.401	82.538	2.575	1.00	14.96	6
ATOM	1196	N	ASP	150	4.336	79.018	1.473	1.00	8.31	7
ATOM	1197	CA	ASP	150	5.084	77.770	1.439	1.00	10.41	6
ATOM	1198	C	ASP	150	5.263	77.507	-0.046	1.00	14.13	6
ATOM	1199	O	ASP	150	6.383	77.457	-0.546	1.00	14.47	8
ATOM	1200	CB	ASP	150	4.270	76.643	2.092	1.00	16.03	6
ATOM	1201	CG	ASP	150	5.100	75.391	2.366	1.00	32.05	6
ATOM	1202	OD1	ASP	150	6.334	75.535	2.478	1.00	29.69	8
ATOM	1203	OD2	ASP	150	4.556	74.264	2.459	1.00	42.90	8
ATOM	1204	N	MET	151	4.137	77.462	-0.750	1.00	10.04	7
ATOM	1205	CA	MET	151	4.131	77.223	-2.188	1.00	7.16	6
ATOM	1206	C	MET	151	5.082	78.065	-3.035	1.00	8.71	6
ATOM	1207	O	MET	151	5.952	77.526	-3.711	1.00	8.02	8
ATOM	1208	CB	MET	151	2.716	77.307	-2.756	1.00	5.94	6
ATOM	1209	CG	MET	151	2.625	76.556	-4.057	1.00	7.34	6
ATOM	1210	SD	MET	151	0.946	76.598	-4.654	1.00	14.54	16
ATOM	1211	CE	MET	151	0.854	78.307	-5.114	1.00	14.81	6
ATOM	1212	N	CYS	152	4.898	79.379	-3.054	1.00	3.52	7
ATOM	1213	CA	CYS	152	5.759	80.212	-3.877	1.00	3.21	6
ATOM	1214	C	CYS	152	7.200	80.045	-3.450	1.00	11.29	6
ATOM	1215	O	CYS	152	8.116	80.096	-4.273	1.00	11.69	8
ATOM	1216	CB	CYS	152	5.428	81.673	-3.634	1.00	5.88	6
ATOM	1217	SG	CYS	152	3.882	82.013	-4.511	1.00	15.11	16
ATOM	1218	N	GLN	153	7.378	79.958	-2.138	1.00	14.90	7
ATOM	1219	CA	GLN	153	8.723	79.859	-1.585	1.00	20.31	6
ATOM	1220	C	GLN	153	9.352	78.540	-2.033	1.00	30.29	6
ATOM	1221	O	GLN	153	10.572	78.434	-2.126	1.00	38.73	8
ATOM	1222	CB	GLN	153	8.732	79.948	-0.049	1.00	23.45	6
ATOM	1223	CG	GLN	153	8.311	81.258	0.624	1.00	36.01	6
ATOM	1224	CD	GLN	153	9.476	82.154	0.997	1.00	78.48	6
ATOM	1225	OE1	GLN	153	9.352	83.380	1.037	1.00	63.01	8
ATOM	1226	NE2	GLN	153	10.627	81.541	1.249	1.00	97.50	7
ATOM	1227	N	SER	154	8.538	77.533	-2.333	1.00	21.34	7
ATOM	1228	CA	SER	154	9.075	76.214	-2.651	1.00	19.80	6
ATOM	1229	C	SER	154	9.059	75.614	-4.054	1.00	20.18	6
ATOM	1230	O	SER	154	9.953	74.842	-4.401	1.00	17.06	8
ATOM	1231	CB	SER	154	8.459	75.177	-1.707	1.00	27.35	6
ATOM	1232	OG	SER	154	8.297	75.684	-0.394	1.00	26.56	8
ATOM	1233	N	MET	155	7.992	75.845	-4.811	1.00	17.15	7
ATOM	1234	CA	MET	155	7.845	75.197	-6.112	1.00	14.65	6
ATOM	1235	C	MET	155	8.926	75.317	-7.182	1.00	19.51	6
ATOM	1236	O	MET	155	9.130	74.413	-8.000	1.00	18.48	8
ATOM	1237	CB	MET	155	6.477	75.472	-6.726	1.00	13.40	6
ATOM	1238	CG	MET	155	6.155	74.511	-7.849	1.00	15.34	6
ATOM	1239	SD	MET	155	4.688	75.191	-8.598	1.00	20.67	16
ATOM	1240	CE	MET	155	3.412	74.578	-7.542	1.00	18.68	6
ATOM	1241	N	TRP	156	9.598	76.461	-7.160	1.00	14.87	7
ATOM	1242	CA	TRP	156	10.628	76.777	-8.132	1.00	12.29	6
ATOM	1243	C	TRP	156	11.887	77.134	-7.369	1.00	19.10	6
ATOM	1244	O	TRP	156	12.637	78.027	-7.755	1.00	21.50	8
ATOM	1245	CB	TRP	156	10.152	77.970	-8.957	1.00	10.35	6
ATOM	1246	CG	TRP	156	9.094	77.518	-9.896	1.00	7.70	6
ATOM	1247	CD1	TRP	156	7.742	77.733	-9.824	1.00	9.86	6
ATOM	1248	CD2	TRP	156	9.310	76.607	-10.971	1.00	4.35	6
ATOM	1249	NE1	TRP	156	7.107	77.002	-10.801	1.00	8.86	7
ATOM	1250	CE2	TRP	156	8.048	76.313	-11.524	1.00	7.66	6
ATOM	1251	CE3	TRP	156	10.453	76.027	-11.524	1.00	5.13	6

ATOM	1252	CZ2	TRP	156	7.905	75.478	-12.632	1.00	5.02	6
ATOM	1253	CZ3	TRP	156	10.309	75.197	-12.620	1.00	6.19	6
ATOM	1254	CH2	TRP	156	9.041	74.926	-13.157	1.00	6.08	6
ATOM	1255	N	GLY	157	12.111	76.431	-6.269	1.00	18.15	7
ATOM	1256	CA	GLY	157	13.297	76.681	-5.462	1.00	18.35	6
ATOM	1257	C	GLY	157	13.484	78.151	-5.103	1.00	24.74	6
ATOM	1258	O	GLY	157	12.581	78.813	-4.590	1.00	25.36	8
ATOM	1259	N	GLU	158	14.672	78.651	-5.419	1.00	21.48	7
ATOM	1260	CA	GLU	158	15.041	80.024	-5.108	1.00	23.86	6
ATOM	1261	C	GLU	158	14.478	81.096	-6.031	1.00	23.00	6
ATOM	1262	O	GLU	158	14.587	82.284	-5.737	1.00	24.65	8
ATOM	1263	CB	GLU	158	16.564	80.137	-5.074	1.00	27.34	6
ATOM	1264	CG	GLU	158	17.195	79.428	-3.894	1.00	46.00	6
ATOM	1265	CD	GLU	158	18.689	79.652	-3.861	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1266	OE1	GLU	158	19.405	78.954	-4.611	1.00	92.38	8
ATOM	1267	OE2	GLU	158	19.114	80.565	-3.121	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1268	N	SER	159	13.928	80.671	-7.161	1.00	17.21	7
ATOM	1269	CA	SER	159	13.362	81.564	-8.163	1.00	15.14	6
ATOM	1270	C	SER	159	12.570	82.708	-7.539	1.00	14.84	6
ATOM	1271	O	SER	159	12.760	83.885	-7.848	1.00	12.03	8
ATOM	1272	CB	SER	159	12.430	80.744	-9.060	1.00	18.13	6
ATOM	1273	OG	SER	159	13.138	79.700	-9.709	1.00	18.75	8
ATOM	1274	N	PHE	160	11.700	82.347	-6.607	1.00	14.79	7
ATOM	1275	CA	PHE	160	10.870	83.352	-5.961	1.00	16.77	6
ATOM	1276	C	PHE	160	11.011	83.437	-4.440	1.00	24.45	6
ATOM	1277	O	PHE	160	11.323	82.449	-3.771	1.00	23.72	8
ATOM	1278	CB	PHE	160	9.406	83.022	-6.265	1.00	17.86	6
ATOM	1279	CG	PHE	160	9.077	82.993	-7.727	1.00	17.57	6
ATOM	1280	CD1	PHE	160	8.620	81.833	-8.321	1.00	17.13	6
ATOM	1281	CD2	PHE	160	9.199	84.131	-8.501	1.00	20.11	6
ATOM	1282	CE1	PHE	160	8.279	81.807	-9.660	1.00	15.22	6
ATOM	1283	CE2	PHE	160	8.891	84.103	-9.841	1.00	18.78	6
ATOM	1284	CZ	PHE	160	8.418	82.944	-10.421	1.00	14.81	6
ATOM	1285	N	LYS	161	10.701	84.620	-3.914	1.00	20.05	7
ATOM	1286	CA	LYS	161	10.620	84.900	-2.482	1.00	15.15	6
ATOM	1287	C	LYS	161	9.359	85.738	-2.324	1.00	18.56	6
ATOM	1288	O	LYS	161	9.036	86.532	-3.211	1.00	19.53	8
ATOM	1289	CB	LYS	161	11.857	85.629	-1.955	1.00	15.65	6
ATOM	1290	CG	LYS	161	12.125	87.006	-2.527	1.00	27.54	6
ATOM	1291	CD	LYS	161	12.086	88.059	-1.450	1.00	61.35	6
ATOM	1292	CE	LYS	161	13.280	88.982	-1.435	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1293	NZ	LYS	161	13.630	89.573	-0.111	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	1294	N	VAL	162	8.573	85.471	-1.284	1.00	16.39	7
ATOM	1295	CA	VAL	162	7.337	86.226	-1.114	1.00	12.18	6
ATOM	1296	C	VAL	162	7.754	87.498	-0.405	1.00	23.83	6
ATOM	1297	O	VAL	162	8.543	87.466	0.536	1.00	27.59	8
ATOM	1298	CB	VAL	162	6.315	85.552	-0.200	1.00	10.11	6
ATOM	1299	CG1	VAL	162	5.308	86.607	0.234	1.00	8.18	6
ATOM	1300	CG2	VAL	162	5.625	84.426	-0.950	1.00	8.87	6
ATOM	1301	N	SER	163	7.277	88.632	-0.894	1.00	25.02	7
ATOM	1302	CA	SER	163	7.711	89.851	-0.241	1.00	27.94	6
ATOM	1303	C	SER	163	6.829	90.383	0.877	1.00	32.31	6
ATOM	1304	O	SER	163	5.633	90.102	0.982	1.00	34.21	8
ATOM	1305	CB	SER	163	8.151	90.929	-1.236	1.00	36.67	6
ATOM	1306	OG	SER	163	7.134	91.884	-1.483	1.00	37.66	8
ATOM	1307	N	GLU	164	7.504	91.157	1.715	1.00	30.15	7
ATOM	1308	CA	GLU	164	6.928	91.874	2.838	1.00	33.78	6
ATOM	1309	C	GLU	164	6.101	93.026	2.271	1.00	41.54	6
ATOM	1310	O	GLU	164	4.991	93.270	2.748	1.00	45.99	8
ATOM	1311	CB	GLU	164	8.069	92.404	3.707	1.00	37.73	6
ATOM	1312	CG	GLU	164	9.241	92.983	2.916	1.00	71.36	6
ATOM	1313	CD	GLU	164	10.063	91.940	2.172	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1314	OE1	GLU	164	10.334	90.871	2.763	1.00	100.00	8

ATOM	1315	OE2	GLU	164	10.378	92.161	0.980	1.00100.00	8
ATOM	1316	N	SER	165	6.602	93.691	1.229	1.00 35.56	7
ATOM	1317	CA	SER	165	5.852	94.758	0.571	1.00 31.48	6
ATOM	1318	C	SER	165	4.644	94.217	-0.182	1.00 29.90	6
ATOM	1319	O	SER	165	4.612	93.086	-0.665	1.00 36.31	8
ATOM	1320	CB	SER	165	6.695	95.597	-0.394	1.00 35.14	6
ATOM	1321	OG	SER	165	5.869	96.493	-1.128	1.00 34.81	8
ATOM	1322	N	SER	166	3.616	95.043	-0.267	1.00 20.42	7
ATOM	1323	CA	SER	166	2.427	94.615	-0.979	1.00 23.31	6
ATOM	1324	C	SER	166	2.527	95.409	-2.271	1.00 29.26	6
ATOM	1325	O	SER	166	1.743	95.243	-3.204	1.00 28.26	8
ATOM	1326	CB	SER	166	1.204	95.117	-0.213	1.00 35.31	6
ATOM	1327	OG	SER	166	1.334	96.507	0.052	1.00 70.74	8
ATOM	1328	N	CYS	167	3.432	96.377	-2.269	1.00 25.95	7
ATOM	1329	CA	CYS	167	3.497	97.243	-3.431	1.00 24.73	6
ATOM	1330	C	CYS	167	4.748	96.901	-4.212	1.00 32.23	6
ATOM	1331	O	CYS	167	4.753	96.946	-5.440	1.00 38.34	8
ATOM	1332	CB	CYS	167	3.471	98.710	-3.003	1.00 24.05	6
ATOM	1333	SG	CYS	167	3.294	99.881	-4.385	1.00 27.18	16
ATOM	1334	N	LEU	168	5.801	96.519	-3.502	1.00 26.95	7
ATOM	1335	CA	LEU	168	7.045	96.202	-4.191	1.00 29.63	6
ATOM	1336	C	LEU	168	7.206	94.744	-4.599	1.00 32.38	6
ATOM	1337	O	LEU	168	8.238	94.151	-4.293	1.00 32.22	8
ATOM	1338	CB	LEU	168	8.243	96.616	-3.340	1.00 31.45	6
ATOM	1339	CG	LEU	168	8.896	97.932	-3.759	1.00 38.90	6
ATOM	1340	CD1	LEU	168	7.832	99.007	-3.878	1.00 41.80	6
ATOM	1341	CD2	LEU	168	9.934	98.319	-2.722	1.00 43.45	6
ATOM	1342	N	CYS	169	6.230	94.186	-5.312	1.00 23.11	7
ATOM	1343	CA	CYS	169	6.281	92.793	-5.742	1.00 17.30	6
ATOM	1344	C	CYS	169	5.556	92.532	-7.058	1.00 21.17	6
ATOM	1345	O	CYS	169	4.703	93.323	-7.455	1.00 22.61	8
ATOM	1346	CB	CYS	169	5.568	91.966	-4.675	1.00 14.55	6
ATOM	1347	SG	CYS	169	3.969	92.677	-4.176	1.00 14.88	16
ATOM	1348	N	LEU	170	5.834	91.391	-7.686	1.00 15.72	7
ATOM	1349	CA	LEU	170	5.166	91.002	-8.928	1.00 11.28	6
ATOM	1350	C	LEU	170	3.914	90.177	-8.652	1.00 14.64	6
ATOM	1351	O	LEU	170	3.841	89.409	-7.700	1.00 20.52	8
ATOM	1352	CB	LEU	170	6.105	90.279	-9.892	1.00 9.40	6
ATOM	1353	CG	LEU	170	7.455	90.977	-9.991	1.00 14.92	6
ATOM	1354	CD1	LEU	170	8.240	90.330	-11.103	1.00 18.89	6
ATOM	1355	CD2	LEU	170	7.228	92.439	-10.322	1.00 13.60	6
ATOM	1356	N	GLN	171	2.941	90.287	-9.544	1.00 11.58	7
ATOM	1357	CA	GLN	171	1.629	89.686	-9.357	1.00 7.36	6
ATOM	1358	C	GLN	171	1.119	89.304	-10.746	1.00 14.31	6
ATOM	1359	O	GLN	171	-0.059	89.002	-10.942	1.00 12.63	8
ATOM	1360	CB	GLN	171	0.827	90.869	-8.826	1.00 5.61	6
ATOM	1361	CG	GLN	171	-0.649	90.737	-8.565	1.00 30.85	6
ATOM	1362	CD	GLN	171	-1.133	92.079	-8.066	1.00 29.81	6
ATOM	1363	OE1	GLN	171	-2.292	92.257	-7.695	1.00 32.20	8
ATOM	1364	NE2	GLN	171	-0.221	93.047	-8.067	1.00 14.44	7
ATOM	1365	N	MET	172	2.044	89.347	-11.700	1.00 9.56	7
ATOM	1366	CA	MET	172	1.782	89.031	-13.092	1.00 4.39	6
ATOM	1367	C	MET	172	0.539	89.734	-13.619	1.00 7.47	6
ATOM	1368	O	MET	172	-0.410	89.104	-14.061	1.00 12.87	8
ATOM	1369	CB	MET	172	1.751	87.524	-13.348	1.00 3.78	6
ATOM	1370	CG	MET	172	2.748	86.685	-12.571	1.00 5.28	6
ATOM	1371	SD	MET	172	4.479	87.198	-12.577	1.00 15.39	16
ATOM	1372	CE	MET	172	4.404	88.016	-14.098	1.00 15.62	6
ATOM	1373	N	ASN	173	0.561	91.059	-13.593	1.00 5.86	7
ATOM	1374	CA	ASN	173	-0.489	91.882	-14.185	1.00 8.22	6
ATOM	1375	C	ASN	173	0.029	93.312	-14.391	1.00 14.89	6
ATOM	1376	O	ASN	173	1.192	93.585	-14.076	1.00 10.93	8
ATOM	1377	CB	ASN	173	-1.831	91.783	-13.454	1.00 10.13	6

ATOM	1378	CG	ASN	173	-1.837	92.508	-12.119	1.00	24.97	6
ATOM	1379	OD1	ASN	173	-1.284	93.596	-11.975	1.00	23.48	8
ATOM	1380	ND2	ASN	173	-2.486	91.906	-11.131	1.00	26.09	7
ATOM	1381	N	LYS	174	-0.780	94.206	-14.956	1.00	12.93	7
ATOM	1382	CA	LYS	174	-0.328	95.568	-15.240	1.00	12.92	6
ATOM	1383	C	LYS	174	0.393	96.251	-14.084	1.00	20.51	6
ATOM	1384	O	LYS	174	1.401	96.950	-14.266	1.00	18.35	8
ATOM	1385	CB	LYS	174	-1.531	96.429	-15.610	1.00	13.05	6
ATOM	1386	CG	LYS	174	-1.520	96.984	-17.015	1.00	57.14	6
ATOM	1387	CD	LYS	174	-1.016	95.992	-18.045	1.00	82.93	6
ATOM	1388	CE	LYS	174	-0.965	96.635	-19.424	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1389	NZ	LYS	174	0.175	96.166	-20.264	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	1390	N	LYS	175	-0.161	96.043	-12.892	1.00	12.95	7
ATOM	1391	CA	LYS	175	0.387	96.653	-11.688	1.00	9.49	6
ATOM	1392	C	LYS	175	1.883	96.413	-11.610	1.00	14.23	6
ATOM	1393	O	LYS	175	2.627	97.208	-11.031	1.00	16.64	8
ATOM	1394	CB	LYS	175	-0.329	96.156	-10.433	1.00	9.05	6
ATOM	1395	CG	LYS	175	-1.816	96.486	-10.394	1.00	14.48	6
ATOM	1396	CD	LYS	175	-2.415	96.305	-9.006	1.00	33.80	6
ATOM	1397	CE	LYS	175	-3.907	96.001	-9.041	1.00	70.12	6
ATOM	1398	NZ	LYS	175	-4.357	95.217	-7.852	1.00	86.94	7
ATOM	1399	N	ASP	176	2.317	95.327	-12.240	1.00	12.25	7
ATOM	1400	CA	ASP	176	3.733	94.985	-12.209	1.00	13.51	6
ATOM	1401	C	ASP	176	4.477	96.169	-12.826	1.00	19.67	6
ATOM	1402	O	ASP	176	5.672	96.390	-12.586	1.00	16.38	8
ATOM	1403	CB	ASP	176	4.016	93.682	-12.965	1.00	16.54	6
ATOM	1404	CG	ASP	176	3.642	92.425	-12.192	1.00	29.56	6
ATOM	1405	OD1	ASP	176	3.247	92.534	-11.014	1.00	35.80	8
ATOM	1406	OD2	ASP	176	3.747	91.313	-12.758	1.00	24.07	8
ATOM	1407	N	MET	177	3.735	96.953	-13.603	1.00	15.84	7
ATOM	1408	CA	MET	177	4.353	98.104	-14.241	1.00	23.22	6
ATOM	1409	C	MET	177	4.882	99.055	-13.174	1.00	27.09	6
ATOM	1410	O	MET	177	6.022	99.525	-13.216	1.00	25.51	8
ATOM	1411	CB	MET	177	3.345	98.804	-15.147	1.00	30.85	6
ATOM	1412	CG	MET	177	3.674	98.614	-16.624	1.00	42.61	6
ATOM	1413	SD	MET	177	2.933	99.802	-17.780	1.00	54.42	16
ATOM	1414	CE	MET	177	1.177	99.560	-17.442	1.00	52.64	6
ATOM	1415	N	VAL	178	4.027	99.293	-12.187	1.00	21.91	7
ATOM	1416	CA	VAL	178	4.354	100.170	-11.074	1.00	17.07	6
ATOM	1417	C	VAL	178	5.473	99.561	-10.245	1.00	16.24	6
ATOM	1418	O	VAL	178	6.438	100.213	-9.870	1.00	13.34	8
ATOM	1419	CB	VAL	178	3.141	100.296	-10.133	1.00	15.43	6
ATOM	1420	CG1	VAL	178	3.540	101.060	-8.881	1.00	15.35	6
ATOM	1421	CG2	VAL	178	1.941	100.909	-10.844	1.00	11.60	6
ATOM	1422	N	ALA	179	5.310	98.290	-9.907	1.00	16.57	7
ATOM	1423	CA	ALA	179	6.311	97.661	-9.063	1.00	16.80	6
ATOM	1424	C	ALA	179	7.659	97.667	-9.759	1.00	21.14	6
ATOM	1425	O	ALA	179	8.691	97.876	-9.124	1.00	19.89	8
ATOM	1426	CB	ALA	179	5.882	96.243	-8.767	1.00	19.49	6
ATOM	1427	N	ILE	180	7.652	97.346	-11.048	1.00	24.18	7
ATOM	1428	CA	ILE	180	8.910	97.273	-11.778	1.00	25.33	6
ATOM	1429	C	ILE	180	9.547	98.643	-11.668	1.00	35.82	6
ATOM	1430	O	ILE	180	10.753	98.766	-11.470	1.00	34.12	8
ATOM	1431	CB	ILE	180	8.705	96.929	-13.259	1.00	29.35	6
ATOM	1432	CG1	ILE	180	8.809	95.416	-13.419	1.00	30.09	6
ATOM	1433	CG2	ILE	180	9.905	97.422	-14.055	1.00	31.19	6
ATOM	1434	CD1	ILE	180	10.245	94.974	-13.202	1.00	27.88	6
ATOM	1435	N	LYS	181	8.685	99.649	-11.786	1.00	39.92	7
ATOM	1436	CA	LYS	181	9.076	101.047	-11.685	1.00	40.22	6
ATOM	1437	C	LYS	181	9.962	101.198	-10.454	1.00	49.48	6
ATOM	1438	O	LYS	181	10.995	101.862	-10.523	1.00	48.24	8
ATOM	1439	CB	LYS	181	7.818	101.909	-11.570	1.00	42.15	6
ATOM	1440	CG	LYS	181	7.758	103.094	-12.516	1.00	51.62	6

ATOM	1441	CD	LYS	181	9.062	103.873	-12.510	1.00	67.16	6
ATOM	1442	CE	LYS	181	8.876	105.302	-12.999	1.00	83.74	6
ATOM	1443	NZ	LYS	181	7.927	106.079	-12.154	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	1444	N	HIS	182	9.626	100.493	-9.377	1.00	52.19	7
ATOM	1445	CA	HIS	182	10.417	100.551	-8.150	1.00	55.34	6
ATOM	1446	C	HIS	182	11.559	99.580	-7.917	1.00	62.44	6
ATOM	1447	O	HIS	182	12.583	99.974	-7.365	1.00	65.79	8
ATOM	1448	CB	HIS	182	9.538	100.635	-6.909	1.00	60.00	6
ATOM	1449	CG	HIS	182	8.766	101.912	-6.862	1.00	69.54	6
ATOM	1450	ND1	HIS	182	7.633	102.111	-7.620	1.00	75.00	7
ATOM	1451	CD2	HIS	182	9.050	103.099	-6.280	1.00	77.46	6
ATOM	1452	CE1	HIS	182	7.208	103.350	-7.444	1.00	77.65	6
ATOM	1453	NE2	HIS	182	8.047	103.968	-6.631	1.00	78.86	7
ATOM	1454	N	LEU	183	11.389	98.315	-8.282	1.00	58.31	7
ATOM	1455	CA	LEU	183	12.496	97.386	-8.098	1.00	57.65	6
ATOM	1456	C	LEU	183	13.387	97.565	-9.322	1.00	75.29	6
ATOM	1457	O	LEU	183	14.030	96.616	-9.772	1.00	77.57	8
ATOM	1458	CB	LEU	183	11.991	95.948	-8.019	1.00	54.17	6
ATOM	1459	CG	LEU	183	10.524	95.810	-7.625	1.00	50.60	6
ATOM	1460	CD1	LEU	183	10.125	94.370	-7.864	1.00	47.37	6
ATOM	1461	CD2	LEU	183	10.386	96.159	-6.158	1.00	49.20	6
ATOM	1462	N	LEU	184	13.368	98.774	-9.876	1.00	76.29	7
ATOM	1463	CA	LEU	184	14.125	99.146	-11.068	1.00	92.80	6
ATOM	1464	C	LEU	184	13.410	98.869	-12.390	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1465	O	LEU	184	14.033	98.502	-13.386	1.00	98.16	8
ATOM	1466	CB	LEU	184	15.528	98.544	-11.051	1.00	92.01	6
ATOM	1467	CG	LEU	184	16.465	99.359	-10.163	1.00	96.71	6
ATOM	1468	CD1	LEU	184	15.687	100.414	-9.393	1.00	95.39	6
ATOM	1469	CD2	LEU	184	17.535	99.989	-11.036	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1470	OT	LEU	184	14.650	96.382	-12.621	1.00	72.97	8
ATOM	1471	N	GLU	199	11.811	102.428	-0.877	1.00	79.68	7
ATOM	1472	CA	GLU	199	10.749	103.416	-0.715	1.00	79.12	6
ATOM	1473	C	GLU	199	9.406	102.895	-1.206	1.00	71.79	6
ATOM	1474	O	GLU	199	9.186	102.665	-2.396	1.00	62.99	8
ATOM	1475	CB	GLU	199	11.100	104.726	-1.424	1.00	82.15	6
ATOM	1476	CG	GLU	199	12.181	104.600	-2.494	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1477	CD	GLU	199	11.888	103.565	-3.573	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1478	OE1	GLU	199	11.381	102.469	-3.250	1.00	86.02	8
ATOM	1479	OE2	GLU	199	12.194	103.840	-4.752	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1480	N	HIS	200	8.507	102.731	-0.246	1.00	70.98	7
ATOM	1481	CA	HIS	200	7.149	102.279	-0.498	1.00	73.47	6
ATOM	1482	C	HIS	200	6.333	103.426	-1.102	1.00	85.54	6
ATOM	1483	O	HIS	200	5.099	103.389	-1.098	1.00	88.06	8
ATOM	1484	CB	HIS	200	6.551	101.804	0.836	1.00	75.60	6
ATOM	1485	CG	HIS	200	5.835	100.490	0.766	1.00	80.36	6
ATOM	1486	ND1	HIS	200	6.448	99.290	1.052	1.00	82.24	7
ATOM	1487	CD2	HIS	200	4.533	100.201	0.533	1.00	83.90	6
ATOM	1488	CE1	HIS	200	5.562	98.315	0.956	1.00	83.00	6
ATOM	1489	NE2	HIS	200	4.390	98.840	0.649	1.00	83.51	7
ATOM	1490	N	ALA	201	7.032	104.428	-1.634	1.00	79.02	7
ATOM	1491	CA	ALA	201	6.441	105.555	-2.358	1.00	71.86	6
ATOM	1492	C	ALA	201	5.559	104.933	-3.442	1.00	65.10	6
ATOM	1493	O	ALA	201	4.551	105.483	-3.895	1.00	62.49	8
ATOM	1494	CB	ALA	201	7.558	106.352	-3.015	1.00	71.01	6
ATOM	1495	N	CYS	202	6.033	103.762	-3.859	1.00	46.14	7
ATOM	1496	CA	CYS	202	5.385	102.819	-4.752	1.00	36.02	6
ATOM	1497	C	CYS	202	3.874	102.870	-4.531	1.00	40.90	6
ATOM	1498	O	CYS	202	3.072	102.867	-5.468	1.00	38.85	8
ATOM	1499	CB	CYS	202	5.921	101.448	-4.328	1.00	29.39	6
ATOM	1500	SG	CYS	202	5.194	99.967	-5.094	1.00	28.33	16
ATOM	1501	N	GLN	203	3.491	102.898	-3.261	1.00	36.05	7
ATOM	1502	CA	GLN	203	2.081	102.919	-2.908	1.00	37.66	6
ATOM	1503	C	GLN	203	1.323	104.109	-3.487	1.00	42.48	6

ATOM	1504	O	GLN	203	0.166	103.983	-3.892	1.00	40.68	8
ATOM	1505	CB	GLN	203	1.934	102.833	-1.389	1.00	40.04	6
ATOM	1506	CG	GLN	203	1.814	101.411	-0.873	1.00	61.10	6
ATOM	1507	CD	GLN	203	0.547	100.732	-1.371	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1508	OE1	GLN	203	-0.406	101.392	-1.794	1.00	87.07	8
ATOM	1509	NE2	GLN	203	0.537	99.403	-1.327	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	1510	N	LYS	204	1.981	105.265	-3.523	1.00	42.97	7
ATOM	1511	CA	LYS	204	1.370	106.473	-4.072	1.00	43.05	6
ATOM	1512	C	LYS	204	1.193	106.268	-5.575	1.00	42.58	6
ATOM	1513	O	LYS	204	0.088	106.397	-6.111	1.00	38.70	8
ATOM	1514	CB	LYS	204	2.250	107.704	-3.809	1.00	47.25	6
ATOM	1515	CG	LYS	204	2.115	108.351	-2.432	1.00	93.49	6
ATOM	1516	CD	LYS	204	1.030	109.422	-2.350	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1517	CE	LYS	204	0.690	109.810	-0.912	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1518	NZ	LYS	204	1.609	110.824	-0.316	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	1519	N	LYS	205	2.303	105.931	-6.226	1.00	33.84	7
ATOM	1520	CA	LYS	205	2.335	105.663	-7.656	1.00	27.21	6
ATOM	1521	C	LYS	205	1.238	104.647	-7.948	1.00	26.13	6
ATOM	1522	O	LYS	205	0.396	104.841	-8.825	1.00	23.03	8
ATOM	1523	CB	LYS	205	3.695	105.049	-7.981	1.00	27.05	6
ATOM	1524	CG	LYS	205	4.193	105.307	-9.391	1.00	46.00	6
ATOM	1525	CD	LYS	205	5.683	105.001	-9.517	1.00	51.03	6
ATOM	1526	CE	LYS	205	6.538	105.983	-8.733	1.00	75.01	6
ATOM	1527	NZ	LYS	205	7.995	105.780	-8.968	1.00	89.85	7
ATOM	1528	N	LEU	206	1.210	103.574	-7.167	1.00	24.65	7
ATOM	1529	CA	LEU	206	0.200	102.551	-7.397	1.00	25.20	6
ATOM	1530	C	LEU	206	-1.185	103.158	-7.296	1.00	24.74	6
ATOM	1531	O	LEU	206	-2.074	102.860	-8.087	1.00	21.51	8
ATOM	1532	CB	LEU	206	0.346	101.386	-6.418	1.00	27.23	6
ATOM	1533	CG	LEU	206	-0.746	100.316	-6.513	1.00	35.94	6
ATOM	1534	CD1	LEU	206	-1.097	99.828	-7.926	1.00	32.42	6
ATOM	1535	CD2	LEU	206	-0.339	99.155	-5.619	1.00	47.24	6
ATOM	1536	N	LEU	207	-1.339	104.054	-6.330	1.00	33.66	7
ATOM	1537	CA	LEU	207	-2.621	104.705	-6.116	1.00	39.94	6
ATOM	1538	C	LEU	207	-3.039	105.561	-7.302	1.00	38.18	6
ATOM	1539	O	LEU	207	-4.213	105.617	-7.666	1.00	35.07	8
ATOM	1540	CB	LEU	207	-2.556	105.556	-4.852	1.00	44.81	6
ATOM	1541	CG	LEU	207	-3.790	105.207	-4.020	1.00	56.04	6
ATOM	1542	CD1	LEU	207	-3.741	105.974	-2.710	1.00	60.08	6
ATOM	1543	CD2	LEU	207	-5.067	105.479	-4.808	1.00	57.93	6
ATOM	1544	N	LYS	208	-2.048	106.217	-7.896	1.00	34.69	7
ATOM	1545	CA	LYS	208	-2.273	107.046	-9.072	1.00	33.96	6
ATOM	1546	C	LYS	208	-2.575	106.128	-10.248	1.00	38.81	6
ATOM	1547	O	LYS	208	-3.569	106.320	-10.946	1.00	36.63	8
ATOM	1548	CB	LYS	208	-1.021	107.862	-9.393	1.00	36.22	6
ATOM	1549	CG	LYS	208	-1.293	109.035	-10.316	1.00	67.98	6
ATOM	1550	CD	LYS	208	-0.163	110.053	-10.272	1.00	86.65	6
ATOM	1551	CE	LYS	208	-0.424	111.184	-11.254	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1552	NZ	LYS	208	-1.884	111.468	-11.362	1.00	100.00	7
ATOM	1553	N	PHE	209	-1.724	105.125	-10.441	1.00	36.28	7
ATOM	1554	CA	PHE	209	-1.897	104.169	-11.529	1.00	37.96	6
ATOM	1555	C	PHE	209	-3.286	103.573	-11.415	1.00	46.72	6
ATOM	1556	O	PHE	209	-3.964	103.356	-12.419	1.00	46.17	8
ATOM	1557	CB	PHE	209	-0.892	103.023	-11.414	1.00	41.15	6
ATOM	1558	CG	PHE	209	-1.165	101.875	-12.347	1.00	41.69	6
ATOM	1559	CD1	PHE	209	-0.635	101.861	-13.630	1.00	41.12	6
ATOM	1560	CD2	PHE	209	-1.929	100.797	-11.933	1.00	40.92	6
ATOM	1561	CE1	PHE	209	-0.866	100.803	-14.485	1.00	37.79	6
ATOM	1562	CE2	PHE	209	-2.171	99.734	-12.791	1.00	41.64	6
ATOM	1563	CZ	PHE	209	-1.619	99.727	-14.060	1.00	36.60	6
ATOM	1564	N	GLU	210	-3.686	103.290	-10.181	1.00	51.93	7
ATOM	1565	CA	GLU	210	-5.008	102.724	-9.953	1.00	60.15	6
ATOM	1566	C	GLU	210	-6.057	103.719	-10.439	1.00	73.21	6

ATOM	1567	O	GLU	210	-7.094	103.339	-10.978	1.00	72.68	8
ATOM	1568	CB	GLU	210	-5.204	102.370	-8.476	1.00	63.63	6
ATOM	1569	CG	GLU	210	-4.614	101.021	-8.080	1.00	82.76	6
ATOM	1570	CD	GLU	210	-4.208	100.953	-6.618	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1571	OE1	GLU	210	-3.498	101.872	-6.152	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1572	OE2	GLU	210	-4.588	99.972	-5.939	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1573	N	ALA	211	-5.765	105.005	-10.276	1.00	76.93	7
ATOM	1574	CA	ALA	211	-6.686	106.039	-10.730	1.00	79.08	6
ATOM	1575	C	ALA	211	-6.229	106.601	-12.074	1.00	80.73	6
ATOM	1576	O	ALA	211	-5.590	107.652	-12.137	1.00	84.11	8
ATOM	1577	CB	ALA	211	-6.800	107.143	-9.687	1.00	80.78	6
ATOM	1578	N	LEU	212	-6.534	105.885	-13.151	1.00	71.01	7
ATOM	1579	CA	LEU	212	-6.144	106.315	-14.489	1.00	50.63	6
ATOM	1580	C	LEU	212	-6.765	105.368	-15.513	1.00	100.00	6
ATOM	1581	O	LEU	212	-6.101	104.879	-16.416	1.00	100.00	8
ATOM	1582	CB	LEU	212	-4.617	106.359	-14.638	1.00	48.80	6
ATOM	1583	CG	LEU	212	-3.835	107.641	-14.337	1.00	49.00	6
ATOM	1584	CD1	LEU	212	-2.357	107.488	-14.626	1.00	46.94	6
ATOM	1585	CD2	LEU	212	-4.354	108.799	-15.167	1.00	54.13	6
ATOM	1586	OT	LEU	212	-8.684	105.284	-12.706	1.00	75.03	8
ATOM	1587	N1	RFL	220	14.343	75.897	-16.620	1.00	17.70	7
ATOM	1588	C2	RFL	220	15.650	75.812	-16.453	1.00	19.63	6
ATOM	1589	O2	RFL	220	16.319	75.144	-17.241	1.00	21.05	8
ATOM	1590	N3	RFL	220	16.325	76.409	-15.398	1.00	19.57	7
ATOM	1591	C4	RFL	220	15.607	77.165	-14.485	1.00	21.19	6
ATOM	1592	O4	RFL	220	16.235	77.700	-13.572	1.00	25.50	8
ATOM	1593	C4A	RFL	220	14.187	77.286	-14.692	1.00	18.01	6
ATOM	1594	N5	RFL	220	13.458	78.126	-13.933	1.00	17.24	7
ATOM	1595	C5A	RFL	220	12.139	78.252	-14.171	1.00	14.38	6
ATOM	1596	C6	RFL	220	11.426	79.075	-13.300	1.00	12.17	6
ATOM	1597	C7	RFL	220	10.043	79.189	-13.442	1.00	12.20	6
ATOM	1598	C7M	RFL	220	9.255	80.065	-12.492	1.00	11.84	6
ATOM	1599	C8	RFL	220	9.398	78.469	-14.496	1.00	11.57	6
ATOM	1600	C8M	RFL	220	7.906	78.585	-14.683	1.00	10.72	6
ATOM	1601	C9	RFL	220	10.120	77.661	-15.374	1.00	11.29	6
ATOM	1602	C9A	RFL	220	11.500	77.549	-15.227	1.00	13.33	6
ATOM	1603	N10	RFL	220	12.240	76.695	-15.993	1.00	16.91	7
ATOM	1604	C10	RFL	220	13.582	76.589	-15.764	1.00	15.12	6
ATOM	1605	C1*	RFL	220	11.640	75.970	-17.133	1.00	21.42	6
ATOM	1606	C2*	RFL	220	10.968	74.637	-16.823	1.00	23.43	6
ATOM	1607	O2*	RFL	220	11.957	73.769	-16.285	1.00	21.31	8
ATOM	1608	C3*	RFL	220	10.102	74.115	-17.978	1.00	27.30	6
ATOM	1609	O3*	RFL	220	8.695	74.346	-17.775	1.00	23.40	8
ATOM	1610	C4*	RFL	220	10.601	73.077	-19.010	1.00	37.79	6
ATOM	1611	O4*	RFL	220	9.611	72.145	-19.455	1.00	42.72	8
ATOM	1612	C5*	RFL	220	11.885	72.229	-18.981	1.00	41.23	6
ATOM	1613	O5*	RFL	220	11.817	71.039	-19.784	1.00	39.42	8

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